

HEAT WAVE RISK ANALYSIS
AND ITS IMPACT ON THE VULNERABLE
GROUPS OF HUÉRCAL-OVERA

LUGIA PROJECT

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CLIMAAX
climate ready regions

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of the LUGIA project is to improve knowledge of the climate risk associated with heat waves in Huércal-Overa and to provide a scientific basis to guide the municipality's urban adaptation. The previous phase made it possible to characterize the historical and future evolution of extreme heat, confirming a trend towards an increase in the frequency, duration and intensity of heat waves. This second phase has moved on from that general climate diagnosis towards a more local, integrated and operational reading of risk, analysing how urban configuration, materials, vegetation, population vulnerability and citizen perception condition its territorial expression.

The work has been carried out using a multi-scale approach that combines the analysis of the municipality as a whole, the hamlets, the main urban core, the census tracts, regular grids, green areas and individual plant specimens. This combination of scales has made it possible to identify internal differences that would remain hidden when working only with average values, and to distinguish between areas with high thermal exposure, areas with a lower environmental regulation capacity and zones where these conditions also coincide with greater population vulnerability.

Urban configuration and heat exposure

The analysis of land surface temperature confirms that the thermal behaviour of Huércal-Overa shows high spatial variability and is closely related to the configuration and use of the territory. Dry agricultural surfaces, open spaces, mobility areas and certain peripheral sectors show a greater propensity to warming, whereas green and recreational uses and some residential and amenity areas display relatively more moderate temperatures. The differences between land uses are more pronounced than those observed between broad land-cover categories, which indicates that ther-

mal behaviour does not depend solely on the surface material, but also on function, configuration, solar exposure, moisture availability and the presence of vegetation. The spatial analyses also confirm that warm and cool areas form persistent territorial clusters and do not respond to isolated anomalies.

The hamlets show differentiated thermal situations. Las Labores and La Hoya are among the cores with the highest surface temperatures, whereas El Saltador and San Francisco show comparatively more moderate conditions. The main urban core occupies an intermediate position, although relevant differences between census tracts and specific spaces persist within it.

Shade availability is also unevenly distributed. The main deficits appear in open spaces, mobility areas, streets and squares with little tree presence, and peripheral areas exposed to solar radiation. This is especially important because an area may present high thermal discomfort even when its mean surface temperature is not the highest. Shade must therefore be considered an essential urban infrastructure for reducing the population's direct exposure.

The pavement study shows a very marked predominance of asphalt, which accounts for 87.32% of the inventoried paved surface. Its high solar-absorption capacity, together with its territorial extent, makes it one of the main potential factors in heat accumulation in the road network. The results indicate that the thermal improvement of the urban space must combine actions on pavements with an increase in shade, permeability and a reduction of exposed surfaces.

Urban Green Infrastructure

The compilation of a vegetation inventory using artificial intelligence has made it possible to obtain a homogeneous cartographic base of the trees, palms, shrub formations and other plant covers of the urban core and the hamlets. This information has been complemented with the analysis of diversity, cover, vigour, resilience and the potential capacity to generate shade and thermal regulation.

The urban core has 5,696 specimens and high overall diversity, with 93 identified species. However, this richness coexists with limited green cover, equivalent to 5.14% of the analysed area, and with a very uneven distribution among districts. District 3 has the greatest relative cover, whereas District 2 is the main deficit area.

The hamlets generally show plant cover that is higher than that of the urban core, although it is frequently associated with a strong dominance of a single species or with formations of an agricultural character. A larger vegetated surface therefore does not imply greater diversity, resilience or urban functionality.

The results confirm that the presence of vegetation, on its own, does not guarantee significant thermal regulation. Its effectiveness depends on the size and continuity of the canopies, the foliar density, the physiological condition, the location of the specimens and their capacity to persist under future conditions of higher temperature, drought and water stress.

The comparison between the green areas and their surroundings shows a reduced average cooling effect when the spaces are considered as a whole. Nonetheless, the maps of tree cover and surface temperature indicate that dense, continuous plant masses coincide more frequently with thermally more moderate areas. Conversely,

isolated trees, discontinuous tree lines and small or heavily sealed green spaces show a limited capacity to modify the dominant thermal behaviour of their surroundings.

Future planning should therefore not be limited to increasing the number of specimens. It will be necessary to increase the effective canopy surface, reinforce the continuity of the Urban Green Infrastructure, improve the existing green areas and select species capable of maintaining their functionality under the current and future climate conditions of Huércal-Overa.

Population vulnerability and citizen participation

The socioeconomic analysis shows that vulnerability to heat is unevenly distributed and cannot be explained solely by age. The integration of demographic, economic and educational variables has made it possible to generate a combined index that reflects both the population's sensitivity and its adaptive capacity.

The results show that tracts with a similar overall level of vulnerability may present different profiles. In some cases, the presence of an age-sensitive population predominates, whereas in others income or educational level become more important. This differentiation will be relevant for designing measures tailored to the specific causes of vulnerability in each area.

The participatory process, developed through sessions with municipal technical staff, a citizen survey, a collaborative map and communication actions, has made it possible to complement the quantitative analysis with the everyday experience of the population.

The participatory map recorded 55 contributions, concentrated mainly in the central axis of the urban core, the Plaza Mayor, the Carretera de la Estación, the area around the Hospital de la Inmaculada and other frequently used amenities and public spaces. The observations identify squares, routes and paved areas with little shade and vegetation, and show a relevant correspondence with the main patterns obtained through the technical analysis.

Participation has also made it possible to identify specific discomfort points within districts classified overall as having low or moderate risk levels. This demonstrates that the census scale is suitable for prioritising general areas, but it must be complemented with detailed analysis to select specific streets, squares, routes and amenities.

No contributions were recorded in the hamlets. This absence does not imply a lack of thermal

problems, but rather a limitation in the territorial coverage of the participatory process, which will need to be corrected in the next phase.

Territorial integration of risk

The integration of tree cover, total shade availability and surface temperature has made it possible to construct an environmental risk index adapted to the local characteristics of the municipality. This index was subsequently combined with population vulnerability to obtain a socio-environmental reading of risk.

In the urban core, District 4 presents the highest level of environmental risk, as a result of unfavourable conditions of temperature, shade and tree cover. However, when population vulnerability is incorporated, District 1 becomes the main area of high socio-environmental risk.

This difference is one of the central findings of the study: the areas with the worst environmental conditions do not necessarily coincide with those where the potential impact on the population may be greatest. The prioritisation of adaptation measures should not be based solely on locating the hottest spaces, but on identifying where exposure coincides with greater sensitivity or a lower response capacity.

In the hamlets, El Saltador, La Hoya, San Francisco, Santa María de Nieva and Úrcal present a moderate environmental risk, whereas Las Labores reaches a high level. When population vulnerability is incorporated, the six hamlets are classified as having high socio-environmental risk. Las Labores is the most critical case, as it combines unfavourable environmental and social conditions.

These results do not mean that all the cores require the same measures. Risk may originate from different combinations of temperature, shade, tree cover, urban structure and population vulnerability. Actions will need to respond to the specific causes identified in each area.

Conclusion and next steps

The study confirms that the risk associated with heat in Huércal-Overa is territorially complex and depends on the interaction between multiple factors. High temperatures, the scarcity of shade, the predominance of absorbent pavements, limited tree cover, the fragmentation of vegetation and population vulnerability combine differently in each district, hamlet and urban space.

Adaptation will need to focus on the places where several of these factors coincide, distinguishing between areas requiring structural transformations and specific points where a localised intervention can produce significant improvements. The Urban Green Infrastructure is a central tool

for this adaptation, but it must be integrated with actions on pavements, permeability, water management, shading and the design of public space.

The results obtained form the basis for the next phase of the project, focused on developing an Urban Naturalisation Strategy to Combat Heat in Huércal-Overa. This phase will need to define and validate the objectives of the Strategy, identify and assess the opportunity spaces, study the intervention alternatives, assign the most suitable Nature-based Solutions, select adapted plant species and establish a feasible schedule of actions.

The Strategy will make it possible to transform the climate, environmental and social diagnosis into an operational instrument to guide municipal decisions, develop specific projects, prioritise investments and move towards a more shaded, permeable, resilient municipality that is better prepared to protect its population against the increase in extreme heat.

INTRODUCTION

From the general diagnosis to a local reading of risk

The previous phase of the project made it possible to establish an initial scientific basis for understanding the climate risk associated with heat waves in Huércal-Overa. Based on the application of the CLIMAAX tools, together with the analysis of historical climate data, future projections and satellite information, a clear trend was confirmed towards an increase in the frequency, duration and intensity of extreme heat episodes. This diagnosis placed the municipality in a scenario of growing exposure, especially relevant because of its semi-arid climate conditions, high insolation, the recurrence of dry periods and the progressive pressure on water resources.

The results obtained showed that climate change is not an abstract future risk, but a pressure that is already observable on public health, urban habitability and the local economy. The climate projections indicated a significant increase in the annual number of heat-wave days, with particularly critical scenarios under high-emission trajectories. Likewise, the surface-temperature analysis made it possible to identify urban areas with high heat accumulation, confirming the importance of studying risk not only from a general climate perspective, but also from its spatial expression within the urban fabric.

One of the main findings of the previous phase was the concentration of risk in the urban core of Huércal-Overa. The areas where greater thermal exposure, the presence of a vulnerable population and a deficit of plant cover coincide were identified as priority spaces for adaptation. In particular, the analysis highlighted the relevance of the northern, central and southern sectors of the urban core, as well as the axis between the Parque Municipal Adolfo Suárez, the employment office, Avenida Guillermo Reyna and other everyday amenities. These areas combine conditions that

may intensify the impact of heat on the population, especially during prolonged episodes of high temperatures.

Phase I also highlighted the need to move towards a more integrated and local reading of risk. Although the climate and satellite analysis made it possible to delimit zones of exposure and vulnerability, the results pointed to the advisability of incorporating new layers of urban, environmental and social information. These include the structure of the urban fabric, the distribution of impervious surfaces, the availability of shade, the quality and continuity of the Urban Green Infrastructure, the presence of sensitive amenities, the citizen perception of heat in public spaces, and a more specific characterization of social vulnerability that is not limited exclusively to age criteria but also incorporates socioeconomic factors.

The preliminary identification of stakeholders carried out in the previous phase is, within this framework, a fundamental basis for this new stage. That work made it possible to recognise the institutional, social, health, educational, neighbourhood and economic actors that may be affected by the increase in extreme heat or that have the capacity to influence the design, implementation and maintenance of adaptation measures. Building on that basis, the present phase incorporates citizen participation more specifically, understood as a tool to contrast the technical diagnosis, gather local knowledge and identify needs and priorities from the everyday experience of the population.

In this context, the present phase of the report builds on the results already obtained and delves into their territorial and operational dimension. The aim is not to repeat the general climate diagnosis, but to use it as a basis for understanding in greater detail how urban form, vegetation, the uses of public space, social vulnerability and citizen perception condition the population's real

exposure. In this way, the analysis moves from the identification of risk towards the definition of criteria that make it possible to prioritise nature-based climate-adaptation actions.

Climate change as a local urban challenge

This need to descend from the general diagnosis towards an urban reading of risk falls within a broader context. Climate change is one of the main factors of environmental, social and economic transformation of Mediterranean cities. The sustained increase in temperatures, the greater frequency and intensity of extreme heat episodes and the progressive reduction in water availability are modifying the conditions of urban habitability, affecting both the thermal comfort of the population and the functioning of urban and peri-urban ecosystems.

This situation is particularly relevant in Europe, the continent that is warming fastest: since the 1980s, its warming has been approximately twice the global average (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2025). Within this context, southern Europe and the Mediterranean region appear as particularly exposed areas: the European Climate Risk Assessment identifies heat and drought as critical risks for health, ecosystems, water resources, agricultural production, outdoor work and economic activity (EEA, 2024). This vulnerability is related to features inherent to the Mediterranean climate, such as high insolation, the recurrence of dry periods, the irregularity of precipitation and the growing pressure on water resources.

Recent evidence confirms this trend. The European State of the Climate 2024 report notes that 2024 was the warmest year on record in Europe and that the continent reached the second-highest value of days with thermal stress and of tropical nights. In addition, during 2024, 60% of

Europe recorded more days than usual with at least strong thermal stress, and on 17 July, 20% of the continent was under very strong thermal stress, one of the largest daily extents in the series since 1950 (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2025). In these territories, urban adaptation therefore faces particularly demanding conditions, both because of the intensity of the climate impacts and because of the vulnerability of urban and environmental systems. These factors are intensified in consolidated environments, where the presence of impervious surfaces, high-thermal-inertia materials, scarce shade and low plant cover favours heat accumulation and the urban heat island.

The city thus ceases to be merely a space that receives climate impacts and becomes an active system in the generation, amplification or mitigation of risk. The configuration of the urban fabric, the distribution of land uses, the morphology of the streets, the availability of resting spaces, the presence of trees and the continuity of the Urban Green Infrastructure directly condition the population's exposure to heat. For this reason, climate adaptation requires analysing the territory with sufficient resolution to identify not only the general climate trend, but also the internal differences between neighbourhoods, streets, amenities and public spaces.

Extreme heat, vulnerability and urban habitability

In this sense, if the city acts as a system capable of amplifying or mitigating risk, the next step is to understand how that risk affects the population unequally. As set out in the previous phase, extreme heat is one of the climate risks with the greatest direct impact on public health and urban habitability. That analysis addressed its effects on mortality, hospitalisations, well-being and productivity, as well as its particular incidence on certain

population groups. In this second phase, the focus shifts from the general characterization of the health impact towards a more specific reading of urban vulnerability, understood as the result of the interaction between social conditions, the characteristics of the built environment, the availability of vegetation, accessibility to shaded spaces and the real capacity to respond to extreme heat episodes.

Vulnerability to heat does not depend solely on age or health status, but also on the urban and social conditions that modulate the population's real exposure. The availability of shade, proximity to green spaces, housing quality, pedestrian accessibility and the presence of community networks influence the capacity for protection during extreme heat episodes. For this reason, two areas subject to similar climate conditions may present very different levels of risk depending on their urban, environmental and social structure.

From this perspective, urban habitability must be understood as a central dimension of climate adaptation. It is not only about reducing average temperatures or generically increasing green surfaces, but about improving the environmental conditions of the everyday spaces where the population lives, moves, works, studies or stays during heat episodes. Adaptation therefore requires identifying the spaces where high thermal exposure, low plant cover, a shade deficit, the presence of a vulnerable population and high intensity of social use coincide.

This approach makes it possible to move from a descriptive climate assessment to an action-oriented territorial assessment. The combination of satellite data, urban cartography, sociodemographic indicators and citizen-participation processes makes it possible to recognise the municipality's critical points more precisely and to construct a more robust prioritisation basis. The integration of these sources is especially relevant for avoiding

homogeneous responses and designing interventions tailored to the specific needs of each urban area.

The role of the Urban Green Infrastructure in climate adaptation

Building on this territorial reading, the Urban Green Infrastructure appears as one of the main tools for reducing heat exposure and improving the environmental conditions of public space, since it plays a strategic role in the adaptation of cities to climate change. Trees, parks, gardens, green corridors, permeable spaces, street tree lines, renaturalised school courtyards and nearby vegetated areas contribute to reducing surface temperature, generating shade, improving thermal comfort, favouring water infiltration, increasing urban biodiversity and improving the environmental quality of public space.

Its function should not be interpreted solely from an ornamental or landscape perspective, but as an essential urban infrastructure. Unlike other elements of the urban system, vegetation provides multiple, simultaneous ecosystem services: thermal regulation, carbon capture, improvement of air quality, reduction of runoff, support for biodiversity, improvement of psychological well-being and the creation of spaces for social interaction. In scenarios of increasing extreme heat, these services acquire growing value for health, urban equity and municipal resilience.

Nevertheless, the climate effectiveness of the Urban Green Infrastructure depends on its location, composition, physiological condition, structure, cover, connectivity and capacity to persist under future climate conditions. Not all vegetation offers the same level of thermal regulation, nor do all species present the same capacity to adapt to scenarios of higher temperature, drought and water stress. For this reason, the

planning of green infrastructure must rely on scientific criteria that make it possible to assess both its current contribution to urban comfort and its future viability.

In this sense, the present report incorporates the analysis of urban vegetation as a central component of adaptation. The identification of covers, plant typologies, deficit areas, zones with the greatest cooling potential and priority spaces for intervention makes it possible to guide a more precise renaturalisation strategy. This approach makes it easier to move from isolated actions to a systemic vision of the Urban Green Infrastructure as a functional, connected network oriented towards reducing climate risk.

Citizen participation and local knowledge

However, for the planning of the Urban Green Infrastructure to respond effectively to the real conditions of use, exposure and vulnerability of the territory, it is necessary to complement the

technical analysis with local knowledge. Urban climate adaptation cannot be based solely on physical indicators or spatial models. Although these tools make it possible to identify patterns of thermal exposure, environmental deficit and vulnerability, the everyday experience of the population provides a complementary view of the real use of public spaces, the areas perceived as most uncomfortable during heat episodes and the specific needs of the various social groups.

In this context, citizen participation is incorporated as a source of local information capable of enriching and contrasting the technical diagnosis, providing evidence on the social perception of climate risk and facilitating the identification of action priorities. Its methodological development and the main results obtained are presented specifically in the corresponding chapter. Nonetheless, it is worth highlighting from this introductory phase its role as a link between scientific evidence, territorial knowledge and decision-making oriented towards climate adaptation and the improvement of urban comfort.

SCOPE OF WORK

The general objective of this phase is to deepen the local assessment of the climate risk associated with extreme heat in Huércal-Overa, moving from a general climate diagnosis towards a more detailed understanding of the urban, environmental and social factors that condition the population's exposure and the municipality's adaptive capacity. To this end, urban analysis, the Urban Green Infrastructure, social vulnerability and citizen participation are integrated as key elements to guide the identification and prioritisation of future climate-adaptation actions.

The previous phase made it possible to establish an initial basis for the climate and territorial diagnosis of the municipality, identifying trends of rising temperature, the expected evolution of heat waves and the spatial distribution of risk. Likewise, areas of the urban core with greater thermal exposure, vulnerability and a deficit of plant cover were identified, and an initial identification of actors and stakeholders relevant to the project was carried out.

On this basis, the second phase incorporates a more detailed analysis of the urban structure, the Urban Green Infrastructure, social vulnerability and citizen perception. The aim is to characterize more precisely the local factors that influence heat accumulation, the population's exposure and the territory's capacity to provide thermal-comfort conditions.

Territorial scales of analysis

The work is carried out using a multi-scale approach, adapting the spatial unit of analysis to the type of information and the objective of each study. Not all parameters can be adequately interpreted at a single scale, so analyses of the municipality as a whole are combined with more detailed assessments of the urban core.

Depending on the analysis carried out, the results are represented using the following territorial units:

- the municipal area as a whole, to characterize the general patterns of surface temperature, land covers and land uses;
- hamlets, to identify thermal differences between the main territorial areas of the municipality;
- the main urban core, to analyse in greater detail the urban structure, vegetation, built surfaces and shading conditions;
- census tracts, to integrate the climate information with the demographic and socio-economic data of the population;
- regular grids, used in those analyses that require detailed spatial resolution, such as the identification of shade deficits;
- green areas and their immediate surroundings, to assess their possible thermal-regulation effect;
- individual plant specimens, to analyse the structure, resilience and potential ecosystem-service-provision capacity of urban vegetation.

This combination of scales makes it possible to avoid overly general interpretations and to locate internal differences that would remain hidden when working only with average municipal or census values. In this way, it is possible to move from a global characterization of risk to the specific identification of streets, public spaces, green areas or urban sectors with the greatest need for adaptation.

Figure 1. Delimitation of the urban core and correspondence between the territorial identifiers and the census tracts used in the analysis.

Specific objectives

The specific objectives of this phase are:

- To analyse the urban structure of the municipality and those elements of the built fabric that may influence heat accumulation, considering aspects such as land uses, impervious surfaces, urban morphology, public spaces and other urban elements of particular interest.
- To assess the existing Urban Green Infrastructure, considering its distribution, cover, continuity, condition, resilience and potential capacity to provide shade, thermal regulation and other ecosystem services.
- To analyse the relationship between land surface temperature and the physical and functional characteristics of the territory, both at the municipal scale and in the urban core and the census tracts.
- To broaden the analysis of social vulnerability by incorporating demographic, economic and educational variables, generating a combined index at the census-tract scale.
- To incorporate citizens' knowledge and perception into the climate-risk analysis through a participatory process aimed at identifying thermal-discomfort spaces and contrasting them with the results of the technical analysis.
- To integrate the urban, environmental, social and participatory results into a joint territorial reading that makes it possible to identify the priority areas for intervention.

This phase represents a necessary step in moving from the general climate diagnosis towards a more precise and applied working basis. The integration of different scales and sources of information will make it possible to guide the prioritisation of actions and to strengthen the local planning of climate adaptation in Huércal-Overa.

ANALYSIS OF CLIMATIC HAZARDS AND LOCAL PARAMETERS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH HEAT WAVES

4.1. Urban configuration and its relationship with heat waves

The purpose of this chapter is to analyse how the physical and morphological characteristics of the urban environment condition the accumulation, exposure and mitigation of heat during high-temperature episodes. To this end, an integrated reading of land surface temperature, land uses, shade and pavements is incorporated, in order to understand how these elements influence the thermal behaviour of urban space.

The analysis is oriented towards identifying those features of the municipality that may favour the intensification of heat or, conversely, contribute to moderating it in certain areas. Rather than offering an isolated description of urban and climatic variables, this chapter seeks to understand how the physical configuration of the territory conditions the spatial distribution of thermal exposure and the possibilities for mitigation against heat waves. In this way, the urban and climate diagnosis constitutes a fundamental piece for interpreting climate risk from a territorial perspective and guiding future adaptation strategies.

4.1.1. Analysis of land surface temperature in relation to land use in the municipality

Methodology

The aim of the analysis was to determine how land surface temperature relates to the physical and functional characteristics of the land in Huércal-Overa. To this end, surface-temperature data obtained through satellite observation were integrated with the cartography of land covers and

land uses from the Spanish Land Occupation Information System (SIOSE).

The study was carried out at several territorial scales: the municipality as a whole, the hamlets, the main urban core and the census tracts. This approach made it possible to characterize both the general thermal patterns of the municipality and the internal differences between rural, agricultural and urban areas.

Preparation and classification of the territorial information

The cartographic layers were reviewed and harmonised to ensure their spatial compatibility. The process included the correction of geometries, the unification of the reference systems and the intersection of the SIOSE cartography with the municipal boundaries, the hamlets, the urban core and the census tracts.

The original SIOSE classification has a high level of detail, so a functional grouping of the categories was carried out in order to facilitate their interpretation and statistical comparison.

Land covers were grouped into seven categories:

- impervious urban;
- urban green;
- wooded agricultural;
- herbaceous agricultural;
- semi-arid natural;
- water;
- mobility.

Figure 2. Reclassification of the land-use categories derived from SIOSE and distribution of the resulting functional groups.

Land uses, in turn, were grouped into eight categories:

- urban residential;
- productive agricultural;
- industrial and logistics;
- transport and mobility;
- recreational green;
- services and amenities;
- natural;
- transitional.

Land covers describe the physical characteristics of the surface, whereas land uses represent the predominant function of the territory. This distinction makes it possible to differentiate, for example, similar surfaces that present different thermal behaviours because of their activity, configuration or maintenance.

Obtaining and processing the surface temperature

The thermal analysis was carried out using Land Surface Temperature (LST) data derived from satellite images of the Copernicus programme.

Mean products were generated for the months of June, July, August and September. These values were subsequently integrated into a single raster representative of the mean surface temperature of the summer period analysed.

The use of monthly and seasonal averages made it possible to reduce the influence of one-off variations between dates and to obtain a more stable representation of the territory's thermal patterns. The summer average was used as the main variable for comparing the different covers, uses and territorial units.

Temperature was assigned to each polygon using zonal statistics. For each unit, the mean, median, minimum, maximum, standard deviation and number of valid pixels were calculated.

The median was used as the main reference in the comparisons, owing to its lower sensitivity to extreme values.

Statistical and spatial analysis

Temperature differences between categories were assessed using non-parametric statistical tests, suitable for non-normal distributions and groups with different numbers of observations.

The analyses made it possible to determine:

- whether there were significant differences between covers and uses;
- what the magnitude of those differences was;
- which classification had a greater explanatory capacity;
- whether the warm and cool areas formed territorial clusters.

The spatial organisation of temperature was analysed using the global Moran's I index and the local LISA and Getis-Ord G_i^* indicators. These techniques made it possible to identify clusters of high temperatures, clusters of low values and spatial concentrations of warm and cool areas.

The urban core was analysed independently to prevent the weight of the municipality's agricultural and natural surfaces from masking the internal differences of the built fabric. Likewise, an analysis by census tract was carried out in order to facilitate the subsequent integration of thermal exposure with social and demographic variables.

Considerations for interpretation

Land surface temperature is not directly equivalent to air temperature, nor is it in itself a measure of thermal comfort. It represents the radiometric temperature of the surface observed by the sensor and is conditioned by solar exposure, moisture, vegetation, shade, materials and urban geometry.

For this reason, a dry agricultural surface or bare soil may reach higher daytime temperatures than certain consolidated urban areas. This result does not invalidate the existence of urban heat-island processes, but reflects the specific thermal behaviour of each surface at the moment of observation.

Results

General distribution of surface temperature

The analysis showed high spatial and temporal variability of surface temperature in Huércal-Overa.

July presented the highest values of the period analysed, followed by August. During both months, temperatures were high and relatively homogeneous across much of the territory, which indicates a generalisation of surface warming during the episodes of greatest summer intensity.

In June and September, greater differentiation between warm and cool areas was observed. In these months, factors such as soil type, moisture availability, vegetation or solar exposure had a more visible influence on the distribution of temperature.

The average for the summer period made it possible to identify the most persistent thermal patterns. The highest temperatures were concentrated mainly in agricultural areas, open surfaces and sectors with high solar exposure, whereas the most moderate values were located in certain urban zones, green spaces, amenities and areas with greater moisture availability.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of the mean land surface temperature during June, July, August and September, and the average for the summer period.

Influence of land covers and land uses

Agricultural covers recorded the highest mean summer temperatures. The wooded agricultural category reached 33.56 °C, followed by mobility, at 33.55 °C, and herbaceous agricultural, at 33.47 °C.

The lowest temperatures corresponded to urban green, at 32.84 °C, and impervious urban, at 32.64 °C. The difference between the extreme categories was less than 1 °C.

These differences indicate that physical cover influences thermal behaviour, although its capacity

to explain the variability of the municipality as a whole is limited.

The differences were clearer when land uses were analysed. The productive agricultural use presented the highest mean summer temperature, at 33.57 °C, followed by the natural use, at 33.31 °C, and transport and mobility, at 33.08 °C.

The lowest temperatures were recorded in recreational green, at 30.78 °C, and services and amenities, at 30.56 °C. The difference between productive agricultural use and services and amenities reached approximately 3 °C.

Table 1. Temperature distribution by land cover.

Land cover	Mean summer temperature
Wooded agricultural	33.56 °C
Mobility	33.55 °C
Herbaceous agricultural	33.47 °C
Semi-arid natural	33.40 °C
Water	33.14 °C
Urban green	32.84 °C
Impervious urban	32.64 °C

Table 2. Temperature distribution by land use.

Land use	Mean summer temperature
Productive agricultural	33.57 °C
Natural	33.31 °C
Transport and mobility	33.08 °C
Transitional	32.64 °C
Urban residential	32.04 °C
Industrial and logistics	31.86 °C
Recreational green	30.78 °C
Services and amenities	30.56 °C

The results show that the function of the territory has a greater capacity to differentiate thermal behaviour than physical cover considered in isolation. Agricultural and open spaces proved warmer, whereas recreational, residential and amenity uses presented relatively more moderate values.

The statistical analyses confirmed that these differences were not random. The association was clearer for land uses than for land covers and decreased during July, when extreme temperatures tended to homogenise the thermal behaviour of the territory.

Figure 4. Distribution of the mean summer surface temperature by: a) land-cover categories; b) land-use categories.

Differences between hamlets and the urban core

The analysis by hamlet made it possible to confirm that the municipality's thermal patterns present marked territorial variability and that the highest surface temperatures are not concentrated exclusively in the main urban core.

Las Labores and La Hoya presented the highest mean values, whereas El Salvador and San Francisco recorded more moderate conditions. The main urban core showed intermediate values and ranked below several hamlets with an agricultural predominance.

This pattern reflects the influence of dry soils, open surfaces and high solar exposure in certain rural and agricultural areas. It also shows that the analysis of surface heat must consider the municipality as a whole and not only the built space.

The monthly distribution showed greater differentiation between hamlets during June and September. In July and August, temperatures were higher and more homogeneous.

In the urban core, the differences between covers and uses were statistically significant, although of small magnitude.

The highest values were recorded on residual agricultural surfaces, industrial areas and spaces associated with mobility. Conversely, residential, recreational and amenity uses presented lower temperatures and more homogeneous distributions.

Overall, the urban core showed a more uniform thermal structure than the rest of the municipality. Nonetheless, internal differences persisted, associated with land function and the presence of vegetation, shade and exposed surfaces.

Figure 5. Distribution of surface temperature by hamlet during June, July, August and September, and the average for the summer period.

Spatial organisation of warm and cool areas

The spatial-autocorrelation analysis confirmed that surface temperature presents a clear territorial organisation rather than a random distribution.

High values tend to cluster together with other warm areas, whereas low values are concentrated in sectors close to one another. This structure was maintained both at the municipal scale and in the analysis by hamlet and census tract.

The main clusters of high temperatures were located in agricultural and peripheral sectors, where open, dry and exposed surfaces predominate. The clusters of lower temperatures were concentrated in areas of the urban core and in sectors with a greater presence of vegetation, moisture or uses of lower thermal intensity.

The Getis-Ord G_i^* analysis made it possible to identify thermal hotspots mainly in the northern and eastern sectors of the municipality, whereas the coldspots were located above all in the central-south and south of the territory.

Figure 6. Spatial structure of the mean summer surface temperature in Huércal-Overa: a) local clusters identified using LISA; b) hotspots and coldspots identified using Getis-Ord G_i^* .

Differences between census tracts

The analysis by census tract showed marked thermal heterogeneity within the municipality. The difference between the warmest and coolest units exceeded 5 °C in the summer average.

Tract 0405304002, not included in the numbering of the urban-core map since it concentrates the largest agricultural area, presented the highest mean temperature, at 34.22 °C. It was followed by tract 4 (0405302003), at 32.89 °C, and tract 0405305002 (also outside the urban core and likewise not included in that map), at 32.82 °C.

The lowest temperatures were recorded in tract 2 (0405302001), at 29.08 °C; tract 7 (0405303004), at 29.37 °C; and tract 3 (0405302002), at 29.47 °C.

Tract 0405304002 was 3.35 °C above the municipal average, whereas tract 2 (0405302001) presented a difference of -1.79 °C.

These results show that thermal exposure is not homogeneously distributed and that there are sectors with a greater propensity for heat accumulation. The census scale therefore makes it possible to identify priority areas and facilitates the subsequent integration of the thermal analysis with social vulnerability.

As an example, tract 4 (0405302003) presented temperatures ranging approximately between 27.5 °C and 37 °C. The warmest areas were concentrated in the western and northern sectors, whereas the lowest values were located mainly in the south and in corridors associated with water-courses, vegetation or greater surface moisture.

LST Verano - CUSEC 0405302003 (n=7740)

Figure 7. Distribution of the mean summer surface temperature and internal thermal structure of census tract 0405302003.

Summary of the results

The analysis shows a clear relationship between land surface temperature and the territorial configuration of Huércal-Overa.

Agricultural surfaces, dry soils and open spaces presented the highest temperatures. Conversely, green, recreational, residential and amenity uses showed relatively more moderate values.

Land function explained the thermal differences better than physical cover. Whereas the differences between covers were less than 1 °C, the differences between uses reached approximately 3 °C.

Las Labores and La Hoya were among the warmest hamlets, whereas El Saltador and San Francisco presented more moderate conditions. The urban core showed intermediate values and a relatively homogeneous thermal structure.

The spatial analyses confirmed that warm and cool areas form persistent territorial clusters. The hotspots were located mainly in agricultural and peripheral sectors, whereas the coldspots were concentrated in areas with a greater presence of vegetation, moisture or uses of lower thermal intensity.

Finally, the differences of more than 5 °C between census tracts highlight the need to work at detailed scales in order to identify the priority spaces and guide future climate-adaptation measures.

4.1.2. Study of shade in the municipality

Methodology

The aim of the study was to estimate the availability of shade during the summer period in Huércal-Overa, considering both the shade generated by vegetation and that produced by buildings and other tall elements.

Preparation of the spatial information

The analysis was carried out using two digital models from the National Aerial Orthophotography Plan (PNOA):

- a digital surface model, which represents the terrain together with vegetation, buildings and other tall elements;
- a digital terrain model, which represents only the ground surface.

The difference between the two models made it possible to estimate the height of the elements located above the terrain. This information was used as a basis for identifying the objects capable of casting shade.

The resulting model includes both vegetation and buildings. This feature is suitable for the aim of the analysis, since it makes it possible to represent the total shade available in urban and peri-urban space, regardless of the element that generates it.

In order to represent the vertical structure of the vegetation more realistically, two auxiliary layers were generated: one corresponding to the canopy height and another approximating the height of the start of the canopy, making it possible to model the geometry of the trees in a simplified way during the calculation of cast shadows.

Simulation of the shadows

The simulation was carried out using the UMEP Solar Radiation: Shadow Generator tool, integrated into QGIS. This algorithm calculates the position of the shadows for a given date and time based on the height of the elements present and the position of the sun.

Hourly simulations were carried out between 08:30 and 19:30, which made it possible to represent the evolution of shade throughout the day and to detect both the areas with persistent shade and those exposed to the sun for most of the day.

Each simulation generated a map in which the various points of the territory were classified as sunlit or shaded at the moment analysed.

Analysis period

The study covered the period from 1 June to 28 September 2025. Dates were selected on a weekly basis to represent the evolution of sunlight conditions throughout the summer.

For each date, hourly simulations were carried out between 08:30 and 19:30. In total, 216 simulations were generated for each study area. This approach made it possible to incorporate both the daily changes in the position of the sun and the seasonal variations that occur between June and September.

Calculation of shade frequency

Once all the hourly maps had been generated, they were combined to obtain a single result representative of the whole period analysed.

The final product expresses the sunlight frequency of each point of the territory through values ranging from 0 to 1:

- values close to 1 indicate high solar exposure;
- values close to 0 indicate a frequent or persistent presence of shade;
- intermediate values represent zones where shade availability varies according to the time of day or the date.

This result makes it possible to identify easily the spaces with greater solar exposure, the zones with frequent shade and the sectors where shade appears only at certain times.

Considerations for interpretation

The results represent a potential estimate of shade based on the shape and height of the elements present and on the position of the sun.

The analysis does not incorporate factors such as cloud cover, the actual density of the foliage or the seasonal loss of leaves. Nor does it automatically distinguish between shade produced by trees and that generated by buildings.

Despite these limitations, the methodology makes it possible to consistently locate the areas with a shade deficit and provides a useful basis for guiding future actions on climate adaptation, the improvement of public space and the increase of thermal comfort.

Results

The analysis shows an uneven distribution of shading within the urban core of Huércal-Overa. On the map, the darker tones represent the highest levels of shade, whereas the lighter tones indicate low or very low shading and, therefore, greater solar exposure.

General distribution of shading

Most of the area analysed presents high levels of shading. It is estimated that approximately 61.8% corresponds to zones with very high shade and 15.5% to zones with high shade. Overall, around 77.4% of the surface presents high or very high levels of shading.

This high percentage is largely explained by the contribution of the shadows cast by buildings, especially in areas with greater building density. However, this type of shade is not equivalent to that generated by trees, since it lacks the effects associated with plant transpiration, which may favour heat accumulation and contribute to the formation of urban heat islands.

The zones with medium shade represent approximately 11.8%, so that around 89.1% of the area analysed reaches at least a medium level of shading.

Conversely, the surfaces with low shade represent approximately 8.1%, whereas the areas with very low shade or high solar exposure account for around 2.8%. Overall, around 10.9% of the surface presents low or very low shading conditions.

These results indicate a high overall presence of shade in the urban area analysed. Nonetheless, its distribution is irregular and there are specific sectors with greater solar exposure, especially in open spaces, sparsely occupied plots and areas with a lower presence of vegetation or buildings.

Main areas with a shade deficit

The most notable foci of lower shading are located in various sectors of census tracts 4 (0405302003), 3 (0405302002) and 6 (0405303003), which, taken together, present a greater proportion of open surfaces, lower building density or a more limited presence of trees. Conversely, tracts 1 (0405301001) and 2 (0405302001) show more balanced behaviour, with a predominance of well-shaded zones, although they also present localised areas of high solar exposure.

Tracts 4 (0405302003) and 3 (0405302002) stand out for concentrating the most extensive and continuous shade deficits, which could be related to lower plant cover or a more dispersed urban configuration. Tract 6 (0405303003), for its part, also presents relevant deficiencies, although in a more fragmented way and alternating with spaces of medium or high shade. By contrast, tracts 1 (0405301001) and 2 (0405302001) tend to show greater continuity of shaded zones, possibly associated with greater urban compactness or with the presence of shade-casting elements, although they are not free of critical points.

Figure 8. Distribution of total urban shading in the core of Huércal-Overa, represented by a 100 m² grid.

Within each census tract, significant internal differences are observed. In the tracts with the greatest deficits, such as 4 (0405302003) and 3 (0405302002), the areas with lower shading tend to be concentrated in open spaces, undeveloped plots or zones with scarce vegetation, whereas the more consolidated sectors present higher levels of shade. In tract 6 (0405303003), this variability is even more evident, with frequent alternation between well-shaded areas and others with high solar exposure. In tracts 1 (0405301001) and 2 (0405302001), although shading predominates, specific points are also identified, such as squares, wide roads or open spaces, where solar exposure is greater.

The internal distribution is heterogeneous in all cases: within a single census tract, surfaces with very high shade and spaces with high solar exposure may coexist. This heterogeneity highlights the limitations of using only mean values per cen-

sus tract to identify shade deficits. For this reason, analysis using grids and the continuous raster is more suitable for precisely locating shading deficits and establishing more detailed comparisons between urban sectors.

Territorial interpretation

Although the overall percentage of shaded surface is high, it must be borne in mind that the model jointly incorporates the shadows cast by vegetation, buildings and other tall elements. In addition, part of the shading may correspond to the interior of, or the surface occupied by, the buildings themselves.

Therefore, these percentages should not be interpreted directly as the proportion of comfortable pedestrian public space. To identify the priority places for intervention, it will be necessary to cross-reference the result with the road network,

squares, amenities, resting areas and the distribution of the vulnerable population.

Summary of the results

The urban core of Huércal-Overa presents a high overall level of shading: approximately 77.4% of the area analysed shows high or very high shade, and around 89.1% reaches at least a medium level.

However, the analysis identifies specific sectors with a shade deficit, located mainly in open spaces, undeveloped plots and areas with a lower presence of vegetation or buildings. These results highlight the need to reinforce shade in priority spaces, combining vegetation with other urban elements, in order to improve thermal comfort and reduce the population's direct exposure during heat episodes.

4.1.3. Study of pavements in relation to urban heat

Methodology

Approach of the analysis

The aim of the pavement study was to characterize the radiative behaviour of the different surfaces present in the urban space of Huércal-Overa. To this end, two properties directly related to their response to solar radiation and to their capacity to exchange thermal energy with the environment were analysed: solar reflectance and thermal emittance.

The measurements were carried out in two field campaigns, conducted on 28 May and 17 June 2026. In total, 34 pavement samples were characterized, distributed in a balanced way between the two campaigns, with 17 samples analysed in each one.

The selection included a wide variety of surfaces representative of the urban core, including different types of asphalt, asphalt-and-cement mixes, asphalt with fine gravel, cobblestones of different colours and finishes, red tiles, marble tiles, grey paving slabs, white marble, ornamental stone and artificial turf. For each sample, an identification code, the type of material, the street or urban space where it was located and its geographic position were recorded.

The diversity of materials analysed made it possible to compare both broad pavement families and variants associated with colour, texture, composition and surface condition. These factors may significantly modify the amount of solar radiation reflected or absorbed and, consequently, the thermal behaviour of the pavement.

Measurement of solar reflectance

Solar reflectance was determined directly using a Surface Optics 410-Solar portable reflectometer. This parameter represents the proportion of incident solar radiation reflected by the surface.

The values were expressed as a percentage. A high reflectance indicates that the pavement returns a greater proportion of the radiation received to the environment, whereas a low reflectance implies that a larger fraction of that energy is absorbed by the material.

To facilitate the interpretation of the results from the perspective of urban warming, the solar absorptance of each sample was also calculated. As these are opaque materials, whose transmittance can be considered negligible, absorptance was obtained as the complementary value of reflectance:

$$\text{SOLAR ABSORPTANCE (\%)} = 100 - \text{SOLAR REFLECTANCE (\%)}$$

Therefore, pavements with high absorptance have a greater potential capacity to capture incident solar radiation and accumulate energy during the hours of exposure.

Measurement of thermal emittance

Thermal emittance was determined using a Surface Optics ET-100 portable emissometer. This parameter expresses the capacity of a surface to emit energy in the form of thermal radiation compared with a black body at the same temperature.

High emittance values indicate a greater capacity to release energy through long-wave radiation. Nonetheless, the thermal response of each pavement does not depend solely on this property, but on its combination with solar absorptance, conductivity, thermal capacity, roughness, moisture content and exposure conditions.

For this reason, solar reflectance or absorptance and thermal emittance were analysed jointly, avoiding interpreting any of these parameters in isolation as a direct measure of surface temperature.

Data processing

The results were organised by sample, pavement type, field campaign and location. For the final analysis, only the values obtained instrumentally using the solar reflectometer and the thermal emissometer were used.

The exploratory readings calculated from the ratio between reflected and incident radiation were not incorporated into the final results. Although these measurements provided technically coherent values, the procedure applied in the field did not fully reproduce the conditions established by the ASTM E1918-21 standard method. Consequently, those data were considered only as supporting information and not as reference instrumental results.

Based on the 34 valid samples, the different pavement types were compared, paying particular attention to the differences associated with material, colour, finish and state of conservation. This characterization makes it possible to assess the relative capacity of the surfaces to reflect or absorb solar radiation and emit thermal energy, providing an initial basis for interpreting their possible contribution to the warming of urban space.

Results

Distribution of pavements in the urban core

The pavement cartography shows a clear predominance of asphalt in the urban area analysed. This material occupies 375,157.82 m², equivalent to 87.32% of the paved surface, and also represents 86.43% of the total inventoried length. Therefore, the overall thermal behaviour of the road network is conditioned mainly by the radiative and thermal characteristics of asphalt.

Cobblestones are the second most representative type, although with a much lower presence. They occupy 26,924.46 m², corresponding to 6.27% of the surface, and represent 6.63% of the length analysed. Earth surfaces account for 3.56% of the total area, whereas tiles and concrete represent 1.66% and 1.10% respectively. Macadam has a residual representation, below 0.10%.

This distribution shows that possible actions on asphalt pavements would have a far greater territorial impact than interventions on minority materials. Nonetheless, cobblestones, tiles and ornamental stones acquire particular relevance in squares, pavements and resting spaces, where the direct exposure of pedestrians and the length of stay may be greater.

Table 3. Distribution of pavements in the urban area analysed.

Material	Area (m ²)	Area (%)	Length (m)	Length (%)
Asphalt (bituminous mix)	375,157.82	87.32 %	51,038.23	86.43 %
Cobblestone	26,924.46	6.27 %	3,915.44	6.63 %
Earth	15,307.20	3.56 %	2,062.26	3.49 %
Tile	7,150.26	1.66 %	1,295.27	2.19 %
Concrete	4,708.63	1.10 %	677.92	1.15 %
Macadam	381.11	0.09 %	60.38	0.10 %
Total	429,629.48	100.00 %	59,056.91	100.00 %

Solar reflectance and absorptance of the pavements

The 34 samples analysed presented high variability in their capacity to reflect solar radiation. The solar-reflectance values ranged between 10.6% and 49.5%, which corresponds to absorptance values between 89.4% and 50.5%.

Asphalt pavements showed, in general terms, the lowest reflectances. The set of asphalt and asphalt-and-cement samples presented an approximate mean reflectance of 19.0%, equivalent to a mean absorptance of 81.0%. Within this family, new asphalt recorded the minimum reflectance value of the entire study, at 10.6%, which implies that it absorbs approximately 89.4% of the incident solar radiation.

The remaining asphalts analysed presented reflectance values generally between 17.7% and 23.6%. These results show that both the type of mix and the finish and surface condition can modify their radiative response. In particular, new asphalt presented a noticeably greater absorption than older asphalts or those mixed with cement and fine gravel.

Cobblestones showed greater variability, with reflectances ranging between 15.9% and 43.8%. Their mean value was approximately 25.8%, corresponding to an absorptance of 74.2%. Grey and light-grey cobblestones were generally among the most absorbent materials, with reflectances close to 16–23%. Conversely, some combinations of grey and yellow cobblestones and certain yellow cobblestones reached values above 37–43%.

Tiles and marble surfaces presented, overall, the highest reflectances, with an approximate average of 38.7% and a mean absorptance of 61.3%. The light circular tile reached the highest reflectance recorded, at 49.5%, followed by some square red tiles, yellow marble tiles and white marble, with values close to or above 40%.

Nonetheless, the results show that the material alone does not completely determine the radiative behaviour. Colour, texture, the degree of polishing, ageing and the presence of dirt generate important differences even between samples belonging to the same type. For example, red tiles presented reflectances ranging between 33.3%

and 43.5%, whereas yellow cobblestones ranged between 28.3% and 37.2%.

Thermal emittance

The thermal-emittance values were high in practically all the samples, with a range between 91.6% and 96.3%. This lower variability compared with reflectance indicates that the main difference between the pavements analysed lies in the amount of solar radiation they absorb during the day, rather than in their relative capacity to emit long-wave thermal radiation.

Asphalts presented an approximate mean emittance of 94.5%. New asphalt reached the maximum value of the set, at 96.3%. Cobblestones showed a mean emittance close to 94.1%, whereas tiles and marble surfaces presented a slightly lower mean value, close to 92.8%.

A high emittance implies that, once heated, the surface can release energy effectively through thermal radiation. However, this parameter should not be interpreted in isolation. A surface with high emittance may reach high temperatures if it has previously absorbed a large amount of solar radiation, especially when it has low reflectance.

Contribution of pavements to urban warming

The combination of high territorial extent and low reflectance makes asphalt the type with the greatest potential capacity to contribute to daytime urban warming. Although some individual cobblestone or stone samples also present high absorptance values, their surface presence is much smaller.

On average, asphalt absorbs approximately 81% of the incident solar radiation and occupies more than 87% of the paved surface analysed. Therefore, its overall contribution to the urban energy balance is foreseeably greater than that of the other materials. New asphalt is especially unfavourable, presenting an absorptance close to 90%.

Cobblestones constitute an intermediate and heterogeneous category. Dark-grey or low-reflectance cobblestones may show behaviour similar to that of some asphalts, whereas light cobblestones or those combined with yellow tones present lower solar absorption. Consequently, the colour

selection and finish of the material can significantly modify its behaviour against heat.

Light tiles and marbles reflect a greater proportion of solar radiation and, therefore, present a lower potential capacity for surface warming during the day. However, a high reflectance may increase the radiation reflected towards pedestrians and surrounding façades, so the selection of pavements should not be based exclusively on maximising this parameter. Its effect on thermal comfort must be analysed jointly with shade, urban geometry and the use of the space.

Artificial turf presented a low reflectance, of 19.7%, equivalent to an absorptance of 80.3%. Although its presence in the general pavement inventory is not significant, this result shows that it should not be considered equivalent to a living plant surface from a thermal point of view. Lacking evapotranspiration and presenting high solar absorption, it

can reach high surface temperatures during direct exposure to the sun.

Possible contribution to the night-time heat island

The contribution of pavements to the night-time heat island depends on the energy accumulated during the day and on the speed with which it is subsequently released. In this sense, materials with low reflectance and high absorptance have a greater amount of potentially stored energy after the hours of insolation.

Asphalt pavements present the most relevant combination from this perspective: they absorb a high proportion of solar radiation, occupy most of the road space and usually present a significant thermal-storage capacity. Although their emittance is high and allows the release of energy through long-wave radiation, the amount of heat

absorbed during the day and the thermal inertia of the pavement can prolong the emission of heat during the hours after sunset.

For this reason, the predominance of asphalt can contribute both to high daytime surface temperatures and to the maintenance of unfavourable thermal conditions during the night. This effect may be especially relevant in wide streets, car parks, roundabouts and areas with little shade and scarce ventilation.

Dark cobblestones, certain stones and artificial turf also present high absorptances and may contribute to heat storage. However, their overall influence is foreseeably smaller owing to their lower territorial extent or to constructive differences in the lower layers.

Light tiles and marbles, by absorbing a smaller proportion of solar radiation, present in principle a lower availability of energy to release during the night. Nonetheless, the night-time evolution of temperature also depends on other properties not measured directly in this study, such as thermal conductivity, heat capacity, thickness, moisture and the constructive structure of the pavement.

Consequently, the results make it possible to identify solar absorptance as an indicator of the warming potential of the materials, but they do not constitute a direct measurement of their night-time contribution. To quantify this effect precisely, it would be necessary to complement the analysis with hourly records of surface temperature or with measurements of the thermal inertia of the various constructive systems.

4.2. Analysis of the Urban Green Infrastructure and its relationship with heat waves

This section addresses the characterisation of the local plant cover, its spatial distribution, its condition or vigour, and its role in modulating thermal exposure during episodes of extreme heat. The Urban Green Infrastructure is analysed as an essential component of municipal climate adaptation, insofar as it can help to reduce the thermal intensity of urban space through the provision of shade, evapotranspiration, the reduction of surface temperatures and the improvement of thermal comfort.

The analysis combines different complementary approaches: the inventory and characterisation of the existing vegetation, the assessment of its resilience to climate stress, the estimation of its contribution to thermal comfort and the analysis of the relationship between land surface temperature and the presence of green areas. This approach makes it possible to assess both the current distribution of the green infrastructure and its actual functionality against heat waves, identifying areas with greater mitigation capacity and zones where the absence, fragmentation or low vigour of the vegetation may increase the thermal exposure of the population.

4.2.1. Vegetation inventory and analysis of parameters related to the Green Infrastructure

Methodology

Definition of the territorial units for the vegetation analysis

For the analysis of the trees and the tree cover, work was carried out on the urban cores included in the study area: the main core of Huércal-Overa and the hamlets of Úrcal, Santa María de Nieva, San Francisco, Las Labores, La Hoya and El Saltador.

In order to facilitate the cartographic reading of the results, in the urban core of Huércal-Overa the official coding of the census tracts was simplified by assigning an internal numeric identifier. This simplification makes it possible to represent the results more clearly on maps, charts and tables, while maintaining at all times the correspondence with the official census codes.

In the case of the hamlets, each urban core analysed was treated as an independent territorial unit. This decision responds to the need to adapt the analysis to the effective urban scope of each locality, regardless of the fact that several hamlets may form part of the same census tract or district. In this way, the results reflect more precisely the effective territorial distribution of the trees and the tree cover within each study core.

In a complementary manner, for the representation of certain parameters derived from the vegetation analysis, a regular grid of 100 × 100 m was established. This grid made it possible to

aggregate and spatially synthesise the values obtained, generating homogeneous comparison units independent of the administrative or census boundaries. Its use facilitates the identification of intra-urban patterns, areas of concentration or deficit of vegetation, and spatial differences that could remain hidden when presenting the results only by district or urban core. Consequently, the maps produced using this grid offer a more detailed reading of the distribution of the trees, the plant cover and the remaining indicators analysed. This analysis was applied only to the main population core.

Production of the vegetation inventory

The vegetation inventory and the analysis of the parameters related to the Urban Green Infrastructure were developed with the aim of characterising in detail the plant cover existing in Huércal-Overa and in the hamlets included in the study area. To this end, a vegetation inventory was generated *ex novo* using a methodology based on the integration of automated detection and classification techniques with artificial intelligence and the spectral analysis of very-high-resolution satellite images.

Detection and classification using Artificial Intelligence

The first phase of the work consisted of the identification, delimitation and individualised classification of the main woody-vegetation elements present in the territory. Using artificial-intelligence algorithms, the crowns of trees, palms and shrub formations were detected, obtaining for each element its location and spatial delimitation. Likewise, the process made it possible to advance in their taxonomic classification, identifying the plant species when the resolution and the spectral and morphological characteristics of the images allowed a sufficiently reliable assignment.

As a result, a detailed and homogeneous mapping of the existing vegetation was obtained, built specifically for this study and applying the same methodological criteria across the entire territorial scope. This information made it possible to quantify the cover associated with trees and shrub vegetation, analyse its spatial distribution and identify differences between the urban core of Huércal-Overa and the different hamlets.

The resulting layer constituted the spatial basis of the Urban Green Infrastructure analysis and served as a reference for producing the integrated green-cover map. In addition to providing information on the surface occupied by larger woody vegetation, the inventory made it possible to have an approximation of its specific composition, facilitating subsequent analyses related to plant diversity, the provision of shade, the condition of the vegetation and its potential contribution to the thermal regulation of the urban environment.

Spectral analysis of the plant cover

On this basis, spectral information from Maxar WorldView-3 satellite images was incorporated. From these images, two vegetation indices were calculated: the NDVI, or Normalised Difference Vegetation Index, and the SAVI, or Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index. In addition to complementing the information from the individualised inventory, the joint application of these indices made it possible to identify other vegetated surfaces that were not necessarily captured by the AI detection, such as herbaceous meadows, low-growing shrub formations, hedges, gardens and other green areas of smaller structural entity.

Integration of the inventory and the spectral information

The integration between the AI inventory and the spectral information was carried out at two levels. Firstly, spectral information was assigned to the tree and shrub polygons that presented spatial overlap with the layer derived from NDVI-SAVI. Secondly, the green surfaces detected through spectral analysis that did not coincide with the AI inventory were incorporated as complementary plant covers.

To avoid overestimating the total vegetation surface, the areas of overlap with the tree and shrub cover already accounted for by the artificial intelligence were removed beforehand. In this way, the spectral layer only contributed new green surface in those areas not included in the base inventory. Likewise, to minimise the possible underestimation of the green cover arising from small spatial mismatches between layers, differences in resolution, residual georeferencing displacements or effects associated with the satellite image's

acquisition angle, a tolerance buffer of 1.2 m was applied to the reference polygon layer.

The result of this phase was an integrated green-cover layer composed of three major components: trees and palms detected using artificial intelligence, inventoried shrub elements and other plant covers identified through spectral analysis. This layer constitutes the main cartographic basis for quantifying the total surface of green infrastructure present in the study area and differentiating between strict tree cover, woody vegetation and integrated green cover.

Analysis of vigour and leaf development

As a complement to the cover analysis, a specific approach was developed to characterise the relative vigour and the leaf development of the detected vegetation. This phase made it possible to move from a purely superficial reading of the green infrastructure to a functional interpretation based on the spectral response of the vegetation.

To this end, the NDVI and SAVI indices calculated from the Maxar WorldView-3 images were used. The NDVI was used as a general indicator of the presence, density and photosynthetic activity of the vegetation, while the SAVI made it possible to partially adjust the effect of bare or sparsely covered soil, especially relevant in a semi-arid context such as Huércal-Overa, where vegetation may appear in a discontinuous or open manner or with a strong influence of the soil background.

From both indices, a combined NDVI-SAVI matrix was generated, oriented towards representing different degrees of plant cover, apparent density and photosynthetic vigour. This matrix was used as a proxy indicator of the leaf area index (LAI), making it possible to assign each vegetated surface a relative class of leaf development.

In order to facilitate the interpretation of the results, the values derived from the spectral matrix were transformed into a synthetic scale from 1 to 5. This scale represents five relative levels of leaf development and plant vigour, from very low to very high values. The lower classes are associated with sparse vegetation, low leaf density or moderate spectral responses, while the higher classes indicate greater plant density, greater photosynthetic activity and higher leaf development.

The vigour and proxy LAI values were assigned both to the elements detected using artificial intelligence and to the complementary plant covers derived from the spectral analysis. In this way, the final layer makes it possible not only to quantify the green surface, but also to differentiate its relative functional quality, identifying areas of greater or lesser photosynthetic vigour, plant density and leaf development.

Results of the vegetation analysis

General characterisation of vegetation in Huércal-Overa

The urban area of Huércal-Overa has a total of 5,696 specimens of woody vegetation. The inventory reflects high species richness and considerable overall diversity, with a Shannon diversity index close to 3. The most abundant species is *Pinus halepensis*, which represents 18.2 % of the specimens, followed by *Phoenix sp.* and *Olea europaea*. The absence of a strong dominance of a single species indicates a relatively diversified composition across the urban core as a whole.

The inventoried green cover reaches 108,025 m², equivalent to 5.14 % of the urban area analysed. Nevertheless, this cover presents an uneven distribution among the different districts.

Table 4. General vegetation indicators for Huércal-Overa.

Parameter	Value
No. of specimens	5,696
Species richness	93
Shannon index (H')	3.0029
Dominant species	<i>Pinus halepensis</i> (18.2 %)
Green cover (m ²)	108,025
Total area (m ²)	210,010,000
Cover/area ratio (%)	5.14 %

Figure 9. Species distribution in Huércal-Overa.

Distribution of the vegetation by district

The results show relevant differences both in the provision of vegetation and in its diversity and territorial cover. Districts 3 and 4 concentrate the largest number of specimens and the largest green-cover surfaces. However, District 3 presents the highest relative cover, with 9.74 %, while in District 4 the large territorial area reduces this proportion to 4.16 %.

District 6 stands out for presenting the highest species richness, with 50 species, and the highest

Shannon index, with a value of 2.8616. Its composition is also one of the most balanced, given that the dominant species, *Olea europaea*, represents only 16.1 % of the total. By contrast, District 1 presents a higher concentration of *Pinus halepensis*, which accounts for 35.6 % of the specimens.

District 2 constitutes the unit with the lowest plant provision. It has 186 specimens and presents a green cover of 1.35 %, clearly lower than that of the rest of the districts. Districts 5 and 7 also show reduced richness and provision, although their cover ratios are higher, with values close to 4–5 %.

Table 5. Vegetation indicators by district.

Parameter	District 1	District 2	District 3	District 4	District 5	District 6	District 7
No. of specimens	706	186	1,402	2,052	237	890	223
Species richness	30	19	45	45	16	50	16
Shannon index (H')	2.3309	2.2582	2.471	2.6836	2.2956	2.8616	2.3584
Green cover (m ²)	14,794	2,805	34,170	32,258	4,698	14,172	5,128
Total area (m ²)	255,462	207,170	350,790	774,882	119,054	285,600	107,200
Cover ratio (%)	5.79 %	1.35 %	9.74 %	4.16 %	3.94 %	4.96 %	4.78 %

In general terms, District 3 presents the most favourable situation from the point of view of territorial cover, while District 6 stands out for the richness and balance of its specific composition. District 2 constitutes the main deficit area, both for its scarce number of specimens and for its reduced proportion of green cover.

Analysis of the Green Infrastructure in the hamlets

The hamlets generally present a proportionally higher plant cover than that observed in several of the urban districts. Nevertheless, this greater cover does not necessarily imply greater diversity, since in several units there is a marked dominance of species associated with agricultural uses or very homogeneous plant formations.

San Francisco records the highest relative cover, with 12.60 %, followed by Úrcal, with 8.41 %, and Las Labores, with 7.72 %. Úrcal also presents the largest number of specimens, with 3,274, and the highest species richness, with 38 species.

By contrast, El Salvador, Las Labores and Santa María de Nieva present low Shannon indices owing to the high dominance of *Olea europaea*, which represents between 61.4 % and 74.9 % of

the specimens. San Francisco also shows a poorly balanced composition, conditioned by the predominance of *Pinus halepensis*, which reaches 55.0 %.

La Hoya presents a somewhat more balanced composition, although with reduced species richness. Its two main species, *Ziziphus lotus* and *Olea europaea*, show very similar proportions, close to 29 %.

The analysis reveals two distinct patterns. In the urban core, the vegetation presents greater species diversity and a generally more balanced composition, although with important spatial inequalities in cover. In the hamlets, relative cover is frequently higher, but it tends to be associated with more homogeneous formations and a strong dominance of species such as *Olea europaea* or *Pinus halepensis*.

From the point of view of Urban Green Infrastructure planning, the results make it possible to identify as priority areas those districts with lower cover and provision, especially District 2. At the same time, the high dominance observed in some hamlets highlights the advisability of considering not only the vegetation surface, but also its diversity and specific composition.

Table 6. Vegetation indicators for the hamlets.

Parameter	El Salvador	La Hoya	Las Labores	San Francisco	Santa María de Nieva	Úrcal
No. of specimens	692	874	1,467	633	1,502	3,274
Species richness	21	17	19	24	21	38
Shannon index (H')	1.1671	2.0490	1.3647	1.8681	1.3829	2.2373
Green cover (m ²)	11,019	14,087	25,423	22,077	28,393	36,199
Total area (m ²)	186,373	260,399	329,481	175,213	456,833	430,492
Cover ratio (%)	5.91 %	5.41 %	7.72 %	12.60 %	6.22 %	8.41 %

Figure 10. Species distribution in the main hamlets.

Analysis of plant cover

The results obtained show that the integrated green cover of the area of Huércal-Overa and its hamlets reaches a total surface of 63.18 ha. The territory analysed constitutes a total surface of 393.89 ha, so the green cover represents 16.04 % of the study area. This value should be interpreted as an integrated green cover that includes trees, palms, shrubs and other vegetated surfaces detected through spectral analysis.

This figure is not directly comparable with the values obtained in Phase I of the project, where the municipal tree cover was estimated from general

cartographic sources of land use and vegetation. In that phase, values of the order of 6–7 % were identified for the wooded masses of the municipal area: specifically, 7.15 % of “wooded masses (conifers and broadleaves)” according to SIOSE AR 2016, and 6.17 % presence of tree masses in the municipal natural context, according to the characterisation based on the Forest Map of Spain. These values referred to wooded masses or forest cover at the municipal scale, whereas the present analysis focuses on a more delimited urban and hamlet scope and employs a more detailed methodology based on an individualised inventory using artificial intelligence and very-high-resolution spectral analysis.

Figure 11. Plant-cover map of the core of Huércal-Overa.

Therefore, the value of 16.04 % should be understood as an expanded reading of the green infrastructure existing in the area analysed. This integrated green cover incorporates not only tree crowns, but also shrub vegetation, gardens, hedges, herbaceous meadows, low-growing masses and other vegetated surfaces identified through the NDVI-SAVI spectral matrix. Consequently, it does not represent a direct increase with respect to the Phase I figure, but rather a methodologically different estimate, more detailed and oriented towards characterising the entirety of the functional plant cover present in the urban and peri-urban area analysed.

The cover from the inventory generated using artificial intelligence includes 12,411 trees and palms, with an associated surface of 22.83 ha. This surface represents 36.13 % of the total green cover and 5.80 % of the complete study area. This figure constitutes a stricter approximation to the urban tree cover detected within the area analysed, although it is also not directly comparable to the municipal figure of Phase I, owing to the differences in spatial scale, information source and methodological resolution.

Figure 12. Spatial distribution of tree cover (%) by 100 m grid in the urban area of Huércal-Overa.

Figure 13. Spatial distribution of tree density (number of specimens per 100 m grid) in the urban area of Huércal-Overa.

The spatial distribution of the tree cover shows marked heterogeneity within the study area. The greatest covers are concentrated in certain sectors where there is a more consolidated presence of urban trees or green areas, while large areas of the urban fabric present reduced percentages of cover. This pattern reveals significant differences in the potential capacity for shade provision and thermal regulation between different sectors of the municipality.

Tree density complements the information provided by tree cover by reflecting the concentration of specimens present in each urban sector. Although both indicators present a general positive relationship, the differences observed between density and cover make it possible to identify areas where large specimens with high cover capacity predominate, as opposed to others where there is a larger number of individuals but with less-developed crowns.

Alongside this tree cover, 1,728 shrub elements were inventoried, with a total surface of 1.70 ha. This surface is equivalent to 2.68 % of the integrated green cover and 0.43 % of the total area. If trees, palms and shrubs detected using artificial intelligence are considered together, the inventoried woody vegetation reaches 24.52 ha, equivalent to approximately 6.22 % of the study area. This value makes it possible to differentiate the structural cover of woody vegetation from the total integrated green cover.

Most of the green cover corresponds to other vegetated surfaces detected through the NDVI-SAVI spectral matrix. These covers reach a surface of 38.65 ha, which represents 61.18 % of the total green cover and 9.81 % of the study area. This group includes herbaceous meadows, gardens, hedges, small shrub masses and other vegetated surfaces that had not been accounted for as individualised trees or shrubs in the AI inventory.

The high proportion of green covers detected through spectral analysis highlights the importance of complementing inventories based on the individual detection of specimens with spectral methodologies. Without this integration, a substantial part of the green infrastructure, especially that composed of herbaceous vegetation, low-growing formations or landscaped surfaces, could be under-represented in the territorial diagnosis.

Results of the vigour and leaf-development analysis

In relation to the values derived from the ND-VI-SAVI spectral matrix, the results show a relatively balanced distribution between the low-to-intermediate response classes and the classes of greater plant vigour. Classes 1, 2 and 3, associated with very low, low and medium proxy LAI values, together group 57.29 % of the detected green cover. This pattern is consistent with the semi-arid climate context of Huércal-Overa, where seasonal aridity, limited water availability and the presence of herbaceous or low-growing shrub covers favour moderate spectral responses.

Classes 4 and 5, associated with high and very high proxy LAI values, represent 42.70 % of the integrated green cover. This percentage indicates that, although the area presents restrictive climatic constraints, there is a relevant proportion of vegetation with a high spectral response, foreseeably associated with consolidated trees, palms, dense shrub masses, irrigated gardens or green surfaces with better moisture and maintenance conditions.

From a functional point of view, the distribution of the spectral classes indicates that the green infrastructure of the study area presents a relevant superficial presence, but with a majority proportion of covers of low or intermediate development. This suggests that not all the green surface has the same potential capacity to provide ecosystem services associated with thermal comfort, shade, evapotranspiration or microclimatic regulation. The areas with greater leaf development and greater relative vigour are foreseeably those that present greater functional capacity, while the covers with a low spectral response may provide less thermal regulation or be more conditioned by seasonality and water stress.

Overall, the analysis makes it possible to have an integrated green-cover map that combines the precision of individualised detection using artificial intelligence with the capacity of spectral analysis to identify complementary vegetated surfaces and characterise their relative functional condition. This approach provides a solid basis for characterising the Urban Green Infrastructure of Huércal-Overa and its hamlets, assessing its spatial distribution, estimating its relative development and supporting subsequent analyses of resilience, thermal regulation, urban comfort and adaptive planning.

The results reinforce the need to interpret the green infrastructure not only in terms of total surface, but also in terms of its composition, structure and functional quality. The differentiation between trees, shrubs and other plant covers, together with the spectral classification of vigour and leaf development, makes it possible to identify consolidated areas, zones with vegetation of smaller entity and spaces with potential for improvement. This information is especially useful for guiding future actions of maintenance, renaturalisation, increase of tree cover and reinforcement of green connectivity in the municipality.

4.2.2. Study of the resilience of the vegetation

Methodology

The aim of the study was to assess the capacity of the trees and the shrub stratum of Huércal-Overa to maintain their functionality under scenarios of thermal increase, longer duration of episodes of extreme heat and increased aridity.

Urban vegetation plays a fundamental role in climate adaptation through the provision of shade, evapotranspiration and the regulation of temperature. However, its capacity to provide these services depends on the species maintaining adequate physiological functioning in the face of current and future climatic conditions.

The methodology is structured into two complementary approaches. The trees were assessed using an ecophysiological model based on their response to thermal stress, while the shrub stratum was analysed on the basis of its functional tolerance to drought.

Ecophysiological assessment of the trees

The thermal resilience of the trees was assessed using the operational efficiency of Photosystem II, expressed through the parameter F_v/F_m' . This indicator makes it possible to estimate the capacity of the photosynthetic apparatus to maintain its functioning when the plant is subjected to high temperatures.

For each species, two experimental reference values were used:

- a value measured at 20 °C, representative of favourable physiological conditions;
- a value measured at 30 °C, representative of a situation of sustained thermal stress.

The difference between both values made it possible to calculate a specific thermal sensitivity for each species. The greater the reduction in efficiency between 20 °C and 30 °C, the greater the physiological vulnerability of the species to the increase in temperature.

Climate scenarios considered

The model incorporated two operational climate-change scenarios:

- an **intermediate scenario**, with a thermal increase of 2 °C and between 3 and 4 additional days of thermal stress;
- an **extreme scenario**, with a thermal increase of between 3 and 3.5 °C and between 6 and 8 additional days of stress.

These scenarios represent the climate trends identified for Huércal-Overa, characterised by rising temperatures, a greater frequency and duration of heat waves and a reduction in the recovery periods between extreme episodes.

An equivalent daytime temperature of 33 °C was adopted as a reference. From this value, the temperature corresponding to each scenario was estimated and the physiological response of the species was projected as a function of their thermal sensitivity.

Incorporation of the duration of the stress and water availability

In addition to the direct increase in temperature, the model considered the cumulative effect of the duration of the heat episodes. To this end, a physiological-fatigue factor was incorporated that progressively penalises the efficiency of the species as the number of stress days increases.

A simplified water factor of 0.90 was also applied to represent the semi-arid conditions of the municipality and the possible intensification of the water deficit as a consequence of greater irregularity of precipitation.

The combination of temperature, duration of the stress and water availability made it possible to obtain a more realistic estimate of the capacity of each species to maintain its functioning under the projected climatic conditions.

Calculation of the physiological risk

The projected physiological efficiency was compared with the reference situation in order to calculate a Physiological Risk Index, expressed as a percentage of relative loss of functionality.

Four risk levels were established:

- **mild:** efficiency loss of up to 20 %;
- **moderate:** loss greater than 20 % and up to 40 %;
- **severe:** loss greater than 40 % and up to 70 %;
- **critical:** loss greater than 70 %.

This classification made it possible to compare the species and determine which present a greater capacity to maintain their functionality against warming and which may experience significant physiological deterioration.

Integration of the solar exposure of each specimen

The model was subsequently applied at the specimen scale by incorporating the mean daily hours of solar exposure of each tree.

Specimens with fewer than 9 hours of insolation per day were considered to be subject to low or moderate exposure. Trees with 9 hours or more were classified as highly exposed and received

an additional penalty in the calculation of their physiological response.

This adjustment made it possible to differentiate specimens of the same species located in different microclimatic conditions. In this way, a tree located in an open and very sunny space may present a greater risk than another of the same species located in a partially shaded zone.

Functional assessment of the shrub stratum

The resilience of the shrub species was assessed using a functional approach based on their tolerance to drought. This approach was adopted owing to the lower availability of specific experimental ecophysiological information for this type of vegetation.

For each species, a dryness index was used that represents its capacity to withstand prolonged periods of summer water deficit once established.

The species were classified into three groups:

- species with an index greater than 4 were considered functionally resilient and were associated with a mild risk;
- species with an index equal to 4 were classified with moderate resilience and risk;
- species with an index lower than 4 were considered to have limited resilience and were associated with a severe risk.

This criterion facilitates the identification of the shrub species with the greatest capacity to maintain their functionality in a climate context characterised by high temperatures, irregular precipitation and prolonged periods of drought.

Considerations for interpretation

The results represent a comparative estimate of the potential resilience of the species and specimens analysed. They do not constitute an exact prediction of mortality, nor do they replace the direct assessment of the physiological, health or structural condition of the vegetation.

The tree model is based on experimental values of Photosystem II response obtained under controlled conditions. Its application to the municipality makes it possible to compare the relative sensi-

tivity of the species, although the actual response of each specimen may be conditioned by additional factors such as age, size, health condition, soil availability, compaction, irrigation, pruning or competition with other individuals.

The climate scenarios, the reference daytime temperature, the physiological-fatigue factor and the water factor constitute operational simplifications intended to translate the climate trends into the potential functioning of the vegetation. Therefore, the values obtained should be interpreted mainly as relative risk levels and not as absolute physiological thresholds.

The insolation penalty makes it possible to incorporate microclimatic differences between specimens, but it does not consider other local factors such as orientation, the radiation reflected by façades and pavements, ventilation or the actual availability of water in the soil.

In the case of the shrub stratum, the classification is based on functional tolerance to drought and not on specific ecophysiological measurements carried out in the municipality. This approach is suitable for an initial territorial assessment, although it simplifies the variability existing between species, provenances, development stages and maintenance conditions.

Despite these limitations, the methodology provides a consistent basis for comparing species, identifying potentially more vulnerable specimens and guiding the selection, replacement and management of urban vegetation under climate-change scenarios.

Results

The results obtained show relevant differences in the resilience of urban vegetation according to the type of species, the climate scenario considered and the specific microclimatic conditions of each specimen.

In the analysis by tree species, under the intermediate scenario the mild risk level predominates, grouping 56.5 % of the species assessed. This category includes species such as *Albizia julibrissin*, *Citrus sp.*, *Cupressus sempervirens*, *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, *Ficus microcarpa*, *Gleditsia triacanthos*, *Olea europaea*, *Phoenix sp.*, *Pinus halepensis*,

Punica granatum, *Tamarix sp.* and *Washingtonia sp.* This result indicates that a significant part of the trees presents adequate physiological stability under conditions of moderate warming.

17.4 % of the species are classified as moderate risk under the intermediate scenario. This group includes *Ceratonia siliqua*, *Ficus carica*, *Morus alba* and *Prunus dulcis*, species that maintain a certain functional capacity, but show greater sensitivity to sustained heat. For their part, 26.1 % of the species already reach severe risk levels under the intermediate scenario, including *Ficus macrocarpa*, *Jacaranda mimosifolia*, *Populus alba*, *Prunus sp.*, *Schinus molle* and *Tipuana tipu*. These species appear as particularly vulnerable elements within the urban green infrastructure of the municipality.

Under the extreme scenario, a generalised shift towards higher risk categories is observed. The percentage of species with mild risk is reduced to 26.1 %, limited to species with greater thermal tolerance or xerotolerant behaviour, such as *Albizia julibrissin*, *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, *Phoenix sp.*, *Pinus halepensis*, *Tamarix sp.* and *Washingtonia sp.* 30.4 % of the species move to moderate risk, including *Citrus sp.*, *Cupressus sempervirens*, *Ficus microcarpa*, *Gleditsia triacanthos*, *Olea europaea*, *Prunus armeniaca* and *Punica granatum*. Finally, 43.5 % of the species are situated in severe risk, which reveals a substantial loss of physiological stability under conditions of intense thermal

increase and greater persistence of heat waves. The analysis at the specimen scale confirms that the resilience of the trees does not depend solely on the species, but also on the specific conditions of environmental exposure. The incorporation of the individual insolation factor makes it possible to identify relevant differences within the same species, especially in those specimens subjected to high daily solar exposure.

In the intermediate scenario, most of the tree specimens assessed are concentrated at moderate risk levels. Of a total of 12,025 tree specimens analysed, 3,373 specimens present mild risk, which represents 28.0 % of the total; 6,663 specimens are classified as moderate risk, equivalent to 55.4 %; and 1,989 specimens reach severe risk, corresponding to 16.5 %. No specimens at critical risk are identified in this scenario.

In the extreme scenario, the thermal increase and the longer duration of the stress episodes cause a clear intensification of the physiological risk. In this case, 3,036 specimens remain at mild risk, equivalent to 25.2 %; 827 specimens are situated at moderate risk, which represents 6.9 %; 7,274 specimens move to severe risk, reaching 60.5 % of the total; and 888 specimens are classified as critical risk, equivalent to 7.4 %. This result shows that, under an extreme climate scenario, more than two-thirds of the trees assessed could be situated at severe or critical levels of physiological risk.

Figure 14. Spatial distribution of the tree specimens classified as severe risk under the extreme climate scenario (100 m grid).

The spatial distribution of the specimens classified as severe risk shows that this situation is not limited to isolated sectors, but extends across much of the urban core. Although practically all areas present some degree of presence of severely affected specimens, grids with a greater concentration are observed, which reveals a relatively generalised distribution of the physiological vulnerability of the trees to intense-warming scenarios. This pattern makes it possible to identify the areas where it is a priority to reinforce the monitoring, maintenance and adaptation of the green infrastructure.

The results reveal that insolation acts as an amplifying factor of the risk, especially in species with intermediate thermal sensitivity. In these cases, high solar exposure may shift certain specimens towards higher risk categories, even when the species is not initially classified among the most vulnerable. This reinforces the need to incorporate microclimatic criteria into the management

of urban trees, especially in streets, squares and open spaces with a high radiative load.

In order to identify the foci of maximum vulnerability, a cartographic representation was produced based on the aggregation of the specimens classified in the critical-risk category under the most extreme climate scenario considered in the study. The representation using a regular 100-metre grid makes it possible to locate those sectors where the trees most likely to experience severe losses of physiological functionality are concentrated, in the face of conditions of thermal increase and prolongation of heat waves.

Unlike the distribution observed for severe risk, the specimens classified as critical risk appear concentrated in a reduced number of specific grids. This pattern indicates that the maximum levels of vulnerability are not distributed homogeneously, but tend to be located in specific sites

Figure 15. Spatial distribution of the tree specimens classified as critical risk under the extreme climate scenario (100 m grid).

where especially sensitive species and unfavourable microclimatic conditions, such as high solar exposure, converge. These sectors constitute priority areas for the individualised monitoring of the trees and for the planning of actions oriented towards reducing thermal stress and improving their establishment conditions.

As regards the shrub stratum, the results show high functional resilience of the set of species analysed. Most of the species present dryness indices greater than 4, which indicates a good capacity to withstand prolonged conditions of summer water deficit and high temperatures. Among the species classified with mild risk are *Atriplex halimus*, *Bougainvillea glabra*, *Nerium oleander*, *Retama sphaerocarpa*, *Salsola oppositifolia*, *Soda oppositifolia*, *Yucca sp.* and *Ziziphus lotus*. These species present a high suitability for the semi-arid context of Huércal-Overa and are consistent with low-water-consumption gardening strategies.

By contrast, *Pittosporum tobira* presents a dryness index of 3, so it is classified as severe risk from a functional point of view. Its lower tolerance to aridity suggests that its use should be limited to sites with better microclimatic conditions, availability of irrigation or lower thermal exposure.

Overall, the resilience study shows that the urban green infrastructure of Huércal-Overa presents a heterogeneous response to heat waves and climate-change scenarios. While part of the trees and most of the shrub stratum show a reasonable adaptation to hot and dry conditions, there is a relevant set of species and tree specimens with high physiological vulnerability, especially under the extreme scenario. These results make it possible to guide the adaptive planning of urban vegetation, prioritising the monitoring of specimens at severe or critical risk, the improvement of establishment conditions, the reduction

of water and thermal stress, and the future selection of species with greater functional stability against heat.

4.2.3. Provision of comfort and thermal regulation by the vegetation

Methodology

The aim of the analysis was to estimate the potential capacity of the urban vegetation of Huércal-Overa to contribute to heat mitigation, the improvement of pedestrian thermal comfort and the microclimatic regulation of urban space.

The methodology starts from the premise that this contribution does not depend solely on the presence of vegetation, but also on its structural and functional characteristics. The size and density of the crowns, the leaf area, the capacity to cast shade and the interception of radiation directly condition the provision of ecosystem services associated with thermal comfort.

Detection and identification of the specimens

The analysis was developed from the individualised detection of trees and other plant elements carried out in previous phases of the work using artificial-intelligence techniques.

For each detected specimen, a spatial geometry was generated that made it possible to determine its location and approximately delimit the extent of its crown. This information was subsequently cross-referenced with the existing municipal inventory, with the aim of integrating the already-registered specimens and the new detections into a single spatial database.

The combination of both sources made it possible to improve the knowledge of the distribution of urban vegetation and to have an individual unit of analysis for estimating its potential contribution to thermal comfort.

Estimation of biometric parameters

From the geometries obtained, the mean crown diameter was calculated, which was used as the starting variable for estimating other biometric

parameters by means of allometric equations specific to each species or functional group.

The parameters calculated included:

- the diameter at breast height (DBH);
- the total leaf area;
- the aboveground biomass;
- the cover associated with each specimen.

The allometric equations make it possible to relate easily observable variables, such as the size of the crown, with structural characteristics of the vegetation that cannot be measured directly from the image used.

The incorporation of these parameters made it possible to enrich the municipal database, so that each specimen became associated not only with a location, but also with a set of attributes necessary to assess its potential capacity to provide ecosystem services.

Application of the Green Metabolism Matrix

Once the spatial and biometric information had been consolidated, the data were integrated into the Green Metabolism Matrix tool, developed by CESYT within the framework of the CDTI project IDI-20180775 “Green Metabolism. An Innovative System for Planning Territorial Urban Green Infrastructure”.

This tool makes it possible to relate the structural, biometric and functional characteristics of the vegetation with its potential capacity to provide different ecosystem services.

The application of the matrix at the specimen scale made it possible to estimate the differential contribution of the species and the individuals detected, as well as to subsequently aggregate the results by zone, street or territorial unit.

Indicators of comfort and thermal regulation

To assess the contribution of the vegetation to thermal comfort, the following indicators were considered:

- potential shading area;
- plant cover;
- leaf area and leaf area index;
- potential reduction of air temperature;
- potential increase of relative humidity;
- reduction of UVA and UVB radiation;
- reduction of total incident solar radiation;
- annual CO₂ absorption.

The shading area and the plant cover represent the physical capacity of the vegetation to reduce the direct incidence of solar radiation on urban space.

The leaf area and the leaf area index provide information on the quantity and density of leaves present in the crown. These parameters are related to the capacity to intercept radiation, provide shade and favour evapotranspiration processes.

The potential reduction of air temperature and the increase of relative humidity make it possible to approximate the contribution of the vegetation to the microclimatic regulation of the immediate environment.

For their part, the reduction of ultraviolet radiation and of total radiation represents the protective capacity of the crowns against direct solar exposure, one of the factors that most influences people's thermal comfort during heat episodes.

The CO₂ absorption was incorporated as a complementary ecosystem service. Although it does not produce an immediate thermal reduction, it makes it possible to represent the multifunctionality of the green infrastructure and its joint contribution to climate adaptation and mitigation.

Territorial integration of the results

The indicators calculated were incorporated into the spatial vegetation database, associating each specimen with an individualised estimate of its potential contribution.

This information makes it possible to analyse:

- which species and specimens present a greater shading capacity;
- where the largest leaf area is concentrated;
- which zones have a greater potential thermal regulation;
- which sectors present a lower provision of comfort;
- where there are deficits of plant cover and shade.

The results can also be aggregated by street, public space, neighbourhood or census tract, facilitating the identification of priority areas for the conservation, improvement or incorporation of new vegetation.

Considerations for interpretation

The results represent an estimate of the potential capacity of the vegetation to provide comfort and thermal regulation. They are not equivalent to a direct measurement of air temperature, radiant temperature or the thermal comfort experienced by the population.

The automated detection and the delimitation of the crowns may present uncertainties related to the resolution of the images, the overlap between specimens, the presence of shadows or the proximity of the vegetation to buildings and other urban elements.

The allometric equations provide estimates based on mean relationships between crown diameter and other biometric parameters. The precision of the results depends on the availability of equations specific to each species and on the similarity between the reference conditions and the actual characteristics of the specimens of Huércal-Overa.

Likewise, the crown area represents a potential shading capacity, but the effective shade varies according to the height and shape of the tree, the leaf density, the time of year, the time of day and the position of the sun.

The estimates of temperature reduction, humidity and radiation interception should be interpreted as comparative indicators of potential provision. The actual microclimatic response is also conditioned by the availability of water, the physiological

condition of the vegetation, ventilation, urban materials and the configuration of the space.

Finally, the current capacity to provide ecosystem services does not necessarily imply that the specimen can maintain it in the future. The interpretation of these results should be carried out jointly with the analysis of the resilience of the vegetation, since trees with a high current contribution may also present a high vulnerability to the increase in temperature or aridity.

Despite these limitations, the methodology makes it possible to compare in a homogeneous way the potential contribution of the different elements of the green infrastructure, identify zones with a low provision of comfort and guide the planning of actions of conservation, replacement and urban naturalisation.

Results

The analysis of the provision of comfort and thermal regulation was applied to a base of 14,124 plant elements, corresponding to 121 species or functional categories. The results show a relevant contribution of the urban vegetation of Huércal-Overa to the improvement of microclimatic conditions, especially through shading, the reduction of incident radiation and the potential regulation of air temperature.

Overall, the vegetation analysed provides a total estimated shading area of 378,909.67 m², equivalent to approximately 37.89 hectares of potential shade. This area represents an especially relevant magnitude from the point of view of urban adaptation, since plant shade constitutes one of the most effective mechanisms for reducing the direct thermal exposure of the population during episodes of extreme heat. The shading area coincides with the estimated plant cover, which makes it possible to use this indicator as a spatial approximation of the capacity for protection against direct solar radiation.

The total estimated leaf area reaches 1,026,158.29 m², with a mean of 72.83 m² of leaf area per specimen. This parameter is especially important because it reflects the functional capacity of the vegetation to intercept radiation, favour evapotranspiration processes and contribute to the mi-

croclimatic regulation of the urban environment. The existence of a high leaf area indicates that the vegetation acts not only as a physical shade element, but also as an active component in the exchanges of energy and moisture with the urban atmosphere.

The mean results obtained using the Green Metabolism Matrix indicate a mean potential reduction of air temperature of 30.07 %. This value should be interpreted as a modelled indicator of relative capacity for thermal regulation, not as a direct measurement of thermal decrease in degrees Celsius. In comparative terms, it makes it possible to identify the role of the vegetation as a modulating element of the urban microclimate and to differentiate species or plant configurations with greater or lesser potential cooling capacity.

Likewise, a mean estimated increase of relative humidity of 30.26 % is obtained, associated with the contribution of the vegetation to evapotranspiration processes. This result reinforces the importance of plant cover as a regulating element in semi-arid climates, where water availability and the capacity to generate more humid microenvironments may play a significant role in improving thermal comfort during the warmest months.

The spatial distribution of the potential increase of relative humidity reveals the differential capacity of urban vegetation to generate more humid microenvironments through evapotranspiration processes. The greatest contributions are located in areas with greater tree cover and crown development, where the vegetation exerts a more intense microclimatic regulation function.

As regards protection against solar radiation, the vegetation analysed presents high values of potential reduction. The mean reduction of UVA radiation stands at 92.90 %, while the mean reduction of UVB radiation reaches 80.29 %. The mean reduction of total incoming radiation is estimated at 89.69 %. These values reveal the high capacity of urban vegetation to act as a filter against incident radiation, reducing the direct thermal load on people and on exposed urban surfaces.

Figure 16. Spatial distribution of the increase of relative humidity associated with urban vegetation (% per 100 m grid).

Figure 17. Spatial distribution of the potential reduction of total incoming radiation provided by urban vegetation (% per 100 m grid).

Figure 18. Spatial distribution of the potential reduction of UVB+C radiation provided by the tree cover (% per 100 m grid).

The results show that the capacity to reduce incident radiation presents a heterogeneous spatial distribution, concentrating especially in the areas with greater tree development. This ecosystem service is especially relevant in the climate context of Huércal-Overa, as it contributes to reducing the direct thermal load on public space, improving comfort conditions during periods of extreme heat and reducing the exposure of the population to high levels of solar radiation.

In a complementary manner, urban vegetation presents a high capacity to filter short-wave ultraviolet radiation, especially in those sectors with greater crown cover. The reduction of exposure to UVB+C radiation constitutes an additional benefit associated with urban trees, with direct implications both for environmental comfort and for the protection of the population against the effects of prolonged exposure to solar radiation.

From the point of view of the contribution by species, the results show that the provision of shade is concentrated significantly in certain species or functional groups, both for their abundance and

for their structural development. *Olea europaea* constitutes the species with the greatest overall contribution of shading, with 114,274.9 m², which represents approximately 30.2 % of the total estimated shade area. This contribution is mainly explained by its high presence in the municipality, with 4,640 specimens identified, rather than by an especially high individual capacity for thermal reduction.

The second-largest contribution corresponds to *Pinus halepensis*, with 73,818.5 m² of shading, equivalent to 19.5 % of the total. Unlike *Olea europaea*, this species combines a numerous presence, with 1,561 specimens, with a high mean capacity to reduce air temperature, estimated at 36.51 %, and a mean reduction of total incoming radiation of 97.06 %. These results situate *Pinus halepensis* as one of the species of greatest functional relevance for urban thermal regulation.

Phoenix sp. constitutes the third-largest group contributing shade, with 36,567.7 m², equivalent to 9.7 % of the total. It also presents a mean reduction of air temperature of 37.20 % and a mean

increase of relative humidity of 44.98 %, which indicates a notable contribution to microclimatic regulation. Nevertheless, its shading capacity should be interpreted bearing in mind its specific architecture, since palms generate shade of a different geometry and density from that of tree species with a wider crown.

Other species with relevant contributions to the total shading area are *Ceratonia siliqua*, with 15,724.2 m²; *Ziziphus lotus*, with 13,392.7 m²; *Prunus* sp., with 11,619.4 m²; *Ficus microcarpa*, with 10,019.2 m²; *Ficus benjamina*, with 9,929.9 m²; *Washingtonia* sp., with 9,589.9 m²; *Ficus macrocarpa*, with 9,133.5 m²; *Cupressus sempervirens*, with 8,700.0 m²; and *Jacaranda mimosifolia*, with 7,231.8 m². Together, these species make up the main core of the green infrastructure with the greatest potential incidence on urban thermal regulation.

The comparative analysis shows that the most abundant species do not always coincide with those of greatest individual capacity for microclimatic regulation. Some species of the genus *Ficus*, such as *Ficus microcarpa*, *Ficus macrocarpa*, *Ficus benjamina* and *Ficus elastica*, present especially high values of potential reduction of air temperature, close to or above 41 %, as well as high increases of relative humidity, close to 70 %. This suggests a high individual functional capacity, related to the development of dense crowns and a high leaf area. However, their total territorial contribution depends on their number of specimens and on their urban location.

By contrast, species that are very well represented in the municipality, such as *Olea europaea*, present a very high overall contribution to shading owing to their abundance, although their mean values of potential reduction of air temperature are more moderate, around 24.11 %. This result highlights the need to interpret the provision of comfort from a dual perspective: the aggregate contribution at the municipal scale and the individual functional capacity of each species or specimen.

In terms of CO₂ absorption, the vegetation analysed presents a total estimated annual absorption of 502,496.06 kg of CO₂ per year, equivalent to approximately 502.5 tonnes per year. *Olea europaea* again appears as the species with the greatest aggregate contribution, with 192,957.4 kg of

CO₂ per year, followed by *Phoenix* sp., with 49,517.1 kg per year, and *Pinus halepensis*, with 31,957.3 kg per year. Although CO₂ absorption does not constitute a direct indicator of immediate thermal comfort, it reinforces the multiple environmental function of the urban green infrastructure.

The spatial distribution of CO₂ absorption shows a clear concentration of this ecosystem service in those grids with a greater presence and development of urban trees. The highest values coincide with sectors that present a greater density of specimens and a greater accumulated leaf area, reinforcing the role of the green infrastructure as a carbon sink at the local scale.

Overall, the results confirm that the urban vegetation of Huércal-Overa plays a relevant role in the provision of comfort and thermal regulation, especially through the generation of shade, the reduction of incident radiation and the potential modulation of air temperature and humidity. The high estimated shading area and the high mean values of radiation reduction indicate that the existing green infrastructure constitutes a strategic asset for adaptation to heat waves.

Nevertheless, the results also reveal that this regulating capacity is not distributed homogeneously between species nor, foreseeably, between urban zones. The concentration of an important part of the shading in certain species and specimens implies that the loss, degradation or inadequate replacement of these elements could significantly reduce the thermal-regulation capacity of the municipality. For this reason, the adaptive management of the green infrastructure must consider not only the presence of vegetation, but also its structure, crown development, leaf area, physiological condition and strategic location in relation to the spaces of greatest thermal exposure.

From a planning perspective, the results make it possible to identify several priority lines of action. Firstly, it is advisable to conserve and reinforce those specimens and species with the greatest contribution to shading and to the reduction of radiation, especially when they are located in pedestrian spaces, squares, school routes, waiting areas or zones with high solar exposure. Secondly, it is appropriate to increase tree cover in deficit areas, prioritising species with a high shade capacity, good climatic adaptation and physiological

Figure 19. Spatial distribution of the estimated annual CO₂ absorption by urban vegetation (kg/year per 100 m grid).

stability against heat. Finally, the future selection of species should jointly integrate criteria of climate resilience, thermal-regulation capacity and suitability for the semi-arid context of Huércal-Overa.

In this way, the analysis of the provision of comfort and thermal regulation makes it possible to move from a merely descriptive view of urban vegetation to a functional assessment of its ecosystem services. This approach provides a quantitative basis for guiding decisions on maintenance, replacement, renaturalisation and the design of new green infrastructure, contributing to improving the habitability of urban space during episodes of extreme heat.

Territorial variability of the provision of Ecosystem Services

In order to analyse the territorial variability of the provision of ecosystem services, the urban core of Huércal-Overa and each of the territorial units

considered in the study were assessed independently. For each area, a synthetic profile was produced by means of a radial diagram that integrates the main indicators related to the functionality of the green infrastructure: tree density, tree cover, thermal-regulation capacity, potential increase of relative humidity, reduction of radiation, CO₂ absorption and the general condition of the trees.

The radial diagrams represent normalised values for each indicator. The greater the distance from the centre, the greater the relative capacity of the area analysed to provide the corresponding ecosystem service. The purpose of these profiles is to facilitate the comparison between localities and territorial units, rather than to represent absolute values.

This representation makes it possible to visually compare the relative capacity of each area to provide ecosystem services linked to adaptation to heat waves.

Urban core of Huércal-Overa

Figure 20. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of the locality of Huércal-Overa.

The ecosystem-service profile of the urban core of Huércal-Overa is relatively balanced, without very marked differences between indicators. The potential CO₂ absorption constitutes the service with the greatest relative development, followed by the condition of the trees and the increase

of relative humidity. The remaining indicators present intermediate and homogeneous values, which reflects a green infrastructure capable of jointly providing services of climate regulation, protection against radiation and improvement of thermal comfort.

Figure 21. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of District 1 of the locality of Huércal-Overa.

District 1 presents a relatively balanced ecosystem-service profile, although the indicators related to microclimatic regulation stand out especially. The potential reduction of air temperature constitutes the service with the greatest relative development, followed by the potential CO₂ absorption, the increase of relative humidity, tree cover and tree density. For their part,

the indicators associated with the reduction of ultraviolet radiation (UVA and UVB+C) and with the condition of the trees present somewhat more moderate values, although they maintain adequate functional levels. Overall, the district has a green infrastructure capable of providing a balanced contribution to thermal regulation and urban climate comfort.

Figure 22. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of District 2 of the locality of Huércal-Overa.

District 2 presents an ecosystem-service profile dominated by the good condition of the trees, which constitutes the indicator with the greatest relative development. It is followed by the potential CO₂ absorption and tree density, with intermediate values. By contrast, the services linked

to microclimatic regulation show a more limited development. Overall, the district has trees that present a good functional condition, although their distribution and cover reduce the overall capacity to provide ecosystem services associated with thermal comfort.

Figure 23. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of District 3 of the locality of Huércal-Overa.

District 3 presents the most favourable profile of the set of districts analysed. The indicators of tree density, tree cover, potential increase of relative humidity, reduction of air temperature, reduction of ultraviolet radiation (UVA and UV-B+C) and potential CO₂ absorption reach high values and show homogeneous behaviour. The only slightly lower indicator is the condition of the trees, although it is also situated at favoura-

ble levels. This behaviour is explained, to a large extent, by the presence of an extensive green mass corresponding to the Adolfo Suárez park, which concentrates a high quantity of trees and provides an important microclimatic-regulation capacity. Overall, the district constitutes one of the areas with the greatest provision of ecosystem services related to heat mitigation and thermal comfort.

Figure 24. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of District 4 of the locality of Huércal-Overa.

District 4 presents a relatively balanced ecosystem-service profile, although with a lower development than that observed in District 3. The indicators with the greatest relative development are the potential CO₂ absorption and tree density. By contrast, the indicators of reduction of ultraviolet radiation (UVA and UVB+C) are those that present

the lowest values of the profile. This behaviour may be associated with the presence of residential developments with abundant scattered trees and private vegetation, which favour carbon capture and maintain a relatively high tree density, although with a less continuous structure that limits the provision of some climate-regulation services.

Figure 25. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of District 5 of the locality of Huércal-Overa.

District 5 presents an ecosystem-service profile headed by the condition of the trees, which constitutes the indicator with the greatest relative development. It is followed by the potential CO₂ absorption and the potential increase of relative humidity, both with medium values. Tree density

and the indicators of reduction of ultraviolet radiation (UVA and UVB+C) record the lowest values of the district. Overall, the district has trees in good condition but with a more limited capacity to provide some ecosystem services related to protection against radiation and microclimatic regulation.

Figure 26. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of District 6 of the locality of Huércal-Overa.

District 6 presents a more favourable ecosystem-service profile than the previous one, although it shows certain imbalances in terms of service provision. It stands out for a high CO₂ absorption and a high tree density. With the exception of

the attenuation of UVB+C radiation, which is somewhat limited, the remaining parameters present a relatively balanced and favourable distribution for the provision of ecosystem services related to microclimatic regulation.

Figure 27. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of District 7 of the locality of Huércal-Overa.

District 7 presents an ecosystem-service profile in which the potential increase of relative humidity stands out, constituting the indicator with the greatest relative development, followed very closely by the potential CO₂ absorption. The reduction of air temperature, tree density and the condition of the trees reach intermediate values, while tree

cover and the indicators of reduction of ultraviolet radiation (UVA and UVB+C) show the lowest levels of the district. Overall, the district presents a moderate capacity for climate regulation, although the limited tree cover conditions the provision of some ecosystem services, especially those related to protection against solar radiation.

Hamlets

Figure 28. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of the locality of El Saltador.

The hamlet of El Saltador presents an ecosystem-service profile characterised by a high potential CO₂ absorption and a high tree density, which constitute the indicators with the greatest relative development. The remaining services show intermediate and relatively balanced values. By contrast, the condition of the trees presents the

lowest value of the profile, while the reduction of UVB+C radiation constitutes the least-developed ecosystem service. Overall, the hamlet has a green infrastructure with a good structural and carbon-capture capacity, although with room for improvement in the functional quality of the trees and in protection against ultraviolet radiation.

Figure 29. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of the locality of La Hoya.

The hamlet of La Hoya presents a relatively balanced ecosystem-service profile. The indicators with the greatest relative development are tree density and the potential CO₂ absorption, reflecting a good presence of vegetation and a high carbon-capture capacity. The remaining ecosystem services show

intermediate values, without especially marked differences between them. By contrast, the condition of the trees constitutes the indicator with the lowest relative development. Overall, the hamlet has a functional green infrastructure, although with considerable room for improvement.

Figure 30. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of the locality of Las Labores.

The hamlet of Las Labores presents one of the most favourable ecosystem-service profiles of the set of hamlets analysed. Tree density, tree cover, potential CO₂ absorption and the microclimatic-regulation indicators reach high and relatively balanced values. The only indicator that shows a comparatively lower development is the condition

of the trees, which suggests room for improvement in the functional quality and resilience of part of the existing specimens, owing especially to the high presence of Aleppo pine. Overall, the hamlet has a well-developed green infrastructure, with a high capacity to provide ecosystem services related to heat mitigation and climate comfort.

Figure 31. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of the locality of San Francisco.

The hamlet of San Francisco presents a relatively balanced ecosystem-service profile, with high values in tree cover, potential CO₂ absorption and the main microclimatic-regulation indicators, such as the potential reduction of air temperature and the increase of relative humidity. The capacity to reduce UVA and UVB+C radiation also reaches favourable values, although slightly lower. The condition of the trees constitutes the least-developed indicator, which suggests room for improvement in the functional quality of part

of the existing vegetation. This configuration is related, in part, to the composition of the inventoried trees, predominantly dominated by *Olea europaea*, a circumstance that favours a good provision of certain ecosystem services, although it limits the structural and functional diversity of the green infrastructure. Overall, San Francisco has a good capacity for climate regulation, although the progressive diversification of species could reinforce its resilience and broaden the provision of ecosystem services.

Figure 32. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of the locality of Santa María de Nieva.

The hamlet of Santa María de Nieva presents one of the most favourable ecosystem-service profiles of the study area. Tree density, tree cover, potential CO₂ absorption and the indicators associated with microclimatic regulation, such as the potential reduction of air temperature and the increase of relative humidity, which reach high values, stand out especially. In contrast, the condition of the trees constitutes the

least-developed indicator, which suggests that the high current capacity to provide ecosystem services could be conditioned by the future evolution of part of the vegetation. Overall, it has a green infrastructure with a high capacity for climate regulation, although it is advisable to maintain monitoring of the functional condition of the trees in order to preserve that capacity in the medium and long term.

Figure 33. Ecosystem-service profile of the urban trees of the locality of Úrcal.

The hamlet of Úrcal presents a balanced and, in general terms, favourable ecosystem-service profile. Tree density, tree cover and potential CO₂ absorption, which reach the highest values of the set of indicators, stand out especially. Likewise, the services associated with microclimatic regulation, such as the potential reduction of air temperature and the increase of relative humidity, show medium-high levels. By contrast, the reduction of UVA and UVB+C radiation and, especially, the condition of the trees present the lowest values of the profile. Overall, Úrcal has a green infrastructure with a good capacity to provide ecosystem services, although improving the functional condition of the trees would make it possible to reinforce the provision of these services in the medium and long term.

Overall, the territorial analysis reveals that the provision of ecosystem services presents notable differences between the different urban areas of the municipality. While some districts and hamlets concentrate a high thermal-regulation capacity thanks to greater plant cover and the presence of consolidated trees, others show relative deficits associated mainly with a lower tree density or a lower structural diversity. These differences reinforce the advisability of adapting the management strategies of the green infrastructure to the specific characteristics of each area, prioritising both the conservation of the sectors with greater functionality and the reinforcement of those where the provision of ecosystem services is more limited.

4.2.4. Study of surface temperature in relation to the Green Infrastructure

Methodology

The aim of the analysis was to assess whether the green areas of Huércal-Overa present lower surface temperatures than those of their immediate urban surroundings and, therefore, to estimate their capacity to generate a local cooling effect on surface temperature.

Delimitation of the green areas and their surroundings

The study started from the municipal cartography of green areas. Around each space, an external area of 50 metres was generated, used as a reference to represent the thermal conditions of its immediate surroundings.

This comparison made it possible to analyse each green area in relation to the urban space that surrounds it, reducing the influence of the thermal differences existing between different parts of the municipality.

Obtaining the surface temperature

The mean land-surface-temperature products corresponding to June, July, August and September were used, as well as the average for the summer period.

For each green area and for its 50-metre surroundings, the mean surface temperature was calculated. In this way, each green space became associated with an interior thermal value and another corresponding to its immediate surroundings.

Incorporation of the tree cover

To complement the analysis of the green areas, the tree-cover layer derived from the vegetation inventory generated using artificial intelligence was incorporated. This layer represents the horizontal projection of the crowns and makes it possible to analyse the presence of the trees independently of the administrative or functional boundaries of the green areas.

The tree cover was overlaid with the land-surface-temperature cartography to identify patterns of coincidence between tree masses, road alignments, scattered groupings or isolated specimens and the different thermal classes observed in the territory.

This analysis was carried out both for the main urban core of Huércal-Overa and for the hamlets included in the study area.

Calculation of the cooling effect

The potential capacity for thermal mitigation was estimated by means of the difference between the exterior temperature and the interior temperature:

$$\text{COOLING EFFECT} = \text{TEMPERATURE OF THE SURROUNDINGS} - \text{TEMPERATURE OF THE GREEN AREA}$$

Positive values indicate that the interior of the green area presents a temperature lower than that of its surroundings. Values close to zero reflect reduced differences, while negative values indicate that the green space presents a temperature equal to or higher than that of the surrounding area.

The differences were analysed using statistical tests adapted to the distribution of the data, comparing both the set of green areas and each space with its own surroundings.

Considerations for interpretation

The results represent differences in surface temperature and not direct measurements of air temperature or of the thermal comfort perceived by the population.

The observed effect may be conditioned by the size and shape of the green area, the density of the vegetation, the presence of impermeable surfaces, the availability of water and the characteristics of the built environment.

Likewise, the external area of 50 metres constitutes a common reference for all the green areas, although the actual reach of their thermal effect may vary between spaces.

Results

General thermal behaviour of the green areas

The green areas presented a median surface temperature of 30.32 °C for the summer average, with a mean temperature of 30.70 °C and a standard deviation of 1.94 °C.

These values were lower than those recorded in the main agricultural categories and in other open spaces of the municipality, situating the green areas among the surfaces with relatively more moderate thermal behaviour.

The monthly medians were 20.46 °C in June, 48.88 °C in July, 42.33 °C in August and 8.95 °C in September. During July and August, the temperatures were concentrated in relatively narrow ranges, while in June and September greater variability between spaces was observed.

Figure 34. Distribution of land surface temperature in the green areas during June, July, August and September, and the average for the summer period.

Comparison between the green areas and their surroundings

The temperatures recorded inside and outside the green areas showed very similar distributions and a high overlap, which indicates that, at a general scale, both types of surface share comparable thermal conditions during the period analysed. This similarity is reflected both in the medians and in the dispersion of the values, suggesting that the thermal differences are not large enough to generate a clear separation between the two groups when they are considered in aggregate.

The general comparison between both sets did not identify statistically significant differences. Nevertheless, when analysing each green area in relation to its immediate surroundings, a systematic tendency towards slightly lower temperatures in the interior of the vegetated spaces was detected. This pattern, although subtle, is repeated in most cases, which suggests the existence of a local cooling effect associated with the presence of vegetation.

During the summer average, the mean difference was approximately 0.03 °C. Although this difference proved statistically consistent, its magnitude was very small, which indicates that the thermal effect of the green areas, in terms of surface temperature, is limited when assessed globally. This low magnitude may be related to factors such as the reduced size of many green spaces, their fragmentation, the presence of impermeable surfaces in their interior or the thermal influence of the surrounding urban environment.

Therefore, the results indicate that the green areas exert a detectable thermal-moderation effect, but one of low intensity when the municipality as a whole is analysed. This behaviour suggests that, although the vegetation contributes to reducing surface temperature, its capacity to generate significant thermal differences depends to a large extent on the specific characteristics of each space and on its immediate urban context.

Figure 35. Comparison of the mean summer surface temperature in the interior of the green areas and in the immediate surroundings.

The reduced magnitude of the observed effect should not be interpreted as an absence of contribution of the green areas to urban thermal comfort. Surface temperature constitutes only one of the dimensions of urban thermal behaviour and does not reflect other regulation mechanisms associated with vegetation, such as the generation of shade, evapotranspiration or the reduction of the radiant temperature experienced by pedestrians. Likewise, the relatively reduced size of many urban green spaces and the thermal influence of the built environment may limit the thermal contrast observed using satellite images.

Spatial variability of the cooling effect

The cooling effect was not homogeneous between the different green areas. In some of the

spaces represented, local differences close to 0.37 °C were observed in favour of the interior of the green area. In other cases, the differences were practically nil or slightly unfavourable.

The spaces of greater size and continuity tended to present more appreciable thermal differences, while small or isolated zones showed a more limited effect. This relationship should be interpreted as an observed tendency and not as a demonstrated causal relationship.

The results indicate that the presence of vegetation does not in itself guarantee an appreciable thermal reduction. The structure of the space, the plant density and the characteristics of the surroundings condition its regulation capacity.

Figure 36. Spatial distribution of the cooling effect of the green areas with respect to their immediate surroundings.

Spatial relationship between surface temperature and tree cover

The overlay of land surface temperature and tree cover makes it possible to analyse in greater detail the spatial relationship between the presence of trees and the thermal behaviour of the different urban cores. On the maps, the tree cover is represented by the green surfaces, while the surface temperature is classified into four intervals: lower than or equal to 28 °C, between 28 and 30 °C, between 30 and 32.5 °C, and higher than 32.5 °C.

In the urban core of Huércal-Overa, a fragmented distribution of the tree cover is observed, with more relevant concentrations in certain parks, gardens, road alignments and spaces located in the central and southern sectors. The main continuous tree masses coincide, in general terms, with areas of relatively moderate surface temperature, especially within the interval between 28 and 30 °C.

This relationship is clearly appreciated in the main green space of the central area, where the concentration of tree cover is associated with temperatures lower than those recorded in part of the surrounding urban surfaces. Groupings of vegetation are also identified at the southern end of the urban core, which coincide with areas of moderate temperature. These patterns support the existence of a local thermal-regulation effect associated with the larger and more continuous plant masses.

Nevertheless, an important part of the urban trees is distributed in a linear or scattered manner, by means of isolated specimens and small-surface alignments. In these situations, the tree cover does not always appreciably modify the dominant thermal class of its surroundings. This is especially visible in the northern and eastern sectors, where the trees appear integrated into large surfaces with temperatures between 30 and 32.5 °C or, locally, higher than 32.5 °C.

Figure 37. Spatial relationship between land surface temperature and tree cover in the urban core of Huércal-Overa.

The existence of trees within zones with high temperatures does not imply that they lack regulation capacity. The spatial resolution of the thermal information, the size of the crowns and the influence of the surrounding impermeable surfaces may limit the identification of the cooling generated by individual specimens. In addition, the thermal pixel may simultaneously integrate vegetation, pavements, roofs and other surfaces with different radiative behaviours.

In the hamlets, important differences are also observed in the distribution of the tree cover and in its relationship with surface temperature. Las Labores, La Hoya, Santa María de Nieva and Úrcal present large surfaces classified above 32.5 °C, although with different patterns of plant cover.

Las Labores shows a relatively scattered tree cover within a mostly high thermal matrix. The presence of specimens and alignments does not seem to generate an extensive modification of the dominant thermal class, which is consistent with the high environmental risk previously identified for this hamlet.

La Hoya also presents surface temperatures mostly higher than 32.5 °C, with a tree cover distributed in a discontinuous manner. The limited spatial continuity of the crowns reduces their capacity to generate extensive areas of thermal moderation, although they may produce localised effects not visible at the scale of representation used.

Santa María de Nieva presents a longitudinal pattern in which the northern and southern zones show high temperatures, while some central sectors record somewhat more moderate values. The tree cover is distributed in a fragmented manner along the core and presents a greater concentration in certain stretches, without coming to constitute a continuous plant network.

Úrcal shows a high presence of vegetation in comparison with other hamlets. However, much of its area continues to be included in the category above 32.5 °C. In the western sector, somewhat more moderate temperatures are identified, coinciding with a greater density and relative continuity of the tree cover. This pattern suggests that the effect of the vegetation is more perceptible when the crowns form continuous groupings and not only when they appear as isolated elements.

El Salvador and San Francisco present, in general terms, more moderate temperatures than the rest of the hamlets. In both cases, the intervals between 28 and 32.5 °C predominate, although internal differences exist. San Francisco stands out for an important concentration of trees in the central and western sector, associated with relatively moderate thermal surfaces. This result is consistent with the high proportion of green cover previously identified in this hamlet.

El Salvador presents a more heterogeneous distribution, with areas between 28 and 30 °C and sectors that reach values of 30 to 32.5 °C. The tree cover is distributed in a discontinuous manner, although certain groupings coincide with areas of lower surface temperature.

Overall, the maps show that the tree cover tends to coincide with more moderate surface temperatures when it presents sufficient density, size and continuity. However, this pattern weakens in the areas where the trees are very fragmented or surrounded by large impermeable and exposed surfaces.

These results help to interpret the reduced mean difference obtained between the green areas and their surroundings. The presence of vegetation produces local effects, but its capacity to modify thermal behaviour at the territorial scale depends on the surface occupied, the continuity of the crowns and the configuration of the surrounding urban space.

Synthesis of the results

The green areas of Huércal-Overa present, in general terms, surface temperatures lower than those of the main agricultural and open surfaces of the municipality. The comparison with their immediate surroundings showed a tendency towards slightly lower temperatures in the interior of the vegetated spaces, although the mean magnitude of the effect was reduced.

The joint representation of surface temperature and tree cover confirms that the most perceptible effects are located in the plant masses of greater size, density and continuity. In the urban core of Huércal-Overa, the main concentrations of trees located in the central and southern sectors generally coincide with surface temperatures more moderate than those recorded in the surrounding surfaces.

Figure 38. Spatial relationship between land surface temperature and tree cover in the hamlets analysed.

In the hamlets, the relationship presents greater variability. San Francisco and El Saltador show relatively moderate thermal conditions, while Las Labores, La Hoya, Santa María de Nieva and Úrcal present large surfaces with temperatures higher than 32.5 °C. In the latter, the tree cover frequently appears fragmented or integrated into urban and peri-urban matrices with high thermal exposure.

The presence of isolated trees or small alignments is not always sufficient to modify the dominant thermal class at the scale of analysis employed. By contrast, the continuous groupings of crowns present a clearer relationship with the reduction of surface temperature.

The differences observed reveal that the thermal-regulation capacity depends on the configuration of the vegetation and not solely on its presence. From a climate-adaptation perspective, the results suggest prioritising the increase of the continuity and density of the tree cover, the connection between plant masses, the reduction of impermeable surfaces and the improvement of the green spaces located in areas of greater thermal exposure.

4.3. Socioeconomic analysis and its relationship with the vulnerability of the population

In the first phase of the study, the vulnerability of the population to extreme heat was assessed considering exclusively the age structure, as this is one of the factors most directly related to physiological sensitivity to high temperatures. This approach made it possible to identify areas with a greater concentration of potentially vulnerable population, especially older people and other sensitive age groups.

Nevertheless, vulnerability to heat is a complex phenomenon that does not depend solely on demographic characteristics. For this reason, in this second phase of the analysis the approach is broadened by incorporating socioeconomic variables that also make it possible to assess the adaptive capacity of the population and the possible existing territorial inequalities. The aim is to identify those areas of the municipality where thermal exposure coincides not only with greater demographic sensitivity, but also with social conditions that may increase the risk associated with episodes of extreme heat.

The analysis of social vulnerability is fundamental for interpreting climate risk from an integrated perspective. Temperature alone does not determine the final impact of a heat wave on the population; that impact also depends on who is exposed, what level of sensitivity they present and what capacity they have to anticipate, withstand or recover from extreme thermal conditions. For this reason, the incorporation of socioeconomic variables complements the physical analyses of thermal exposure and makes it possible to obtain a more complete view of urban vulnerability.

The analysis is therefore oriented towards detecting zones where three critical dimensions may coincide: high exposure to heat, greater demographic or social sensitivity and a lower adaptive capacity. These areas should be considered priorities for the design of measures of prevention, communication, urban renaturalisation, the generation of climate shelters and the planning of specific actions during episodes of extreme heat.

4.3.1. Generation of a combined vulnerability index

Methodology

The aim of the analysis was to construct a synthetic index capable of representing the social vulnerability of the population of Huércal-Overa to the effects of extreme heat.

Social vulnerability depends on the sensitivity of the population and on its capacity to anticipate, respond to and recover from climate impacts. To approximate these dimensions, demographic, economic and educational variables available homogeneously at the census scale were selected.

Territorial unit of analysis

The index was calculated for each census tract of the municipality, using the CUSEC code as the territorial identifier.

This scale makes it possible to represent the internal differences of Huércal-Overa with a sufficient level of detail and facilitates the comparison between the different areas of the municipality.

Each census tract received a final vulnerability value between 0 and 1, where the highest values represent greater relative vulnerability.

Selection of the social indicators

The index was built from three dimensions:

- age-related vulnerability;
- economic vulnerability;
- educational vulnerability.

Age-related vulnerability was calculated from the combined proportion of population aged 0 to 4 years and aged 65 years or over with respect to the total population of each census tract. Both groups present greater physiological sensitivity to extreme temperatures.

Economic vulnerability was estimated using the mean net income per person. Income levels condition the capacity of households to access adequate housing, air-conditioning systems, health resources and other measures of protection against heat.

Educational vulnerability was calculated using the proportion of population aged 15 years or over with primary education or below. This variable was incorporated as an approximation to the possible differences in access to, understanding of and use of preventive information.

Information sources

The information used comes from the National Statistics Institute of Spain. The following sources were considered:

- Annual population census and continuous register, for the age structure;
- Atlas of Household Income Distribution, for the mean net income per person;
- Annual population census, for the educational level.

The data were collected at the census scale and associated with the cartography of census tracts of the municipality.

Normalisation of the indicators

The original indicators present different units and ranges, so they were transformed to a common scale between 0 and 1 by means of a min-max normalisation.

On this scale:

- values close to 0 represent lower relative vulnerability;
- values close to 1 represent greater relative vulnerability.

Age-related and educational vulnerability were normalised directly, since higher values indicate greater vulnerability.

In the case of income, an inverse normalisation was applied, so that the tracts with lower income obtained values closer to 1.

Weighting and calculation of the index

The three normalised indicators were combined by means of a weighted sum.

Table 7. Weight of each indicator of the vulnerability index.

Indicator	Weight
Age-related vulnerability	45 %
Economic vulnerability	35 %
Educational vulnerability	20 %

The population vulnerability index was calculated using the expression:

$$IVP_d = 0.45 \cdot VE_{norm,d} + 0.35 \cdot VR_d + 0.20 \cdot VEdu_{norm,d}$$

where

IVP_d represents the population vulnerability index of census tract *d*

VE_{norm,d} corresponds to the normalised age-related vulnerability

VR_d represents the normalised and inverted income vulnerability

VEdu_{norm,d} corresponds to the normalised educational vulnerability.

Age-related vulnerability received the greatest weight owing to its direct relationship with physiological sensitivity to heat.

Economic vulnerability received the second-greatest weight, as it represents the material adaptation capacity of the population. The educational dimension was incorporated as a complementary factor related to access to information and preventive resources.

Classification of the index

The values obtained were grouped into five categories to facilitate their cartographic representation:

- very low vulnerability;
- low vulnerability;
- medium vulnerability;
- high vulnerability;
- very high vulnerability.

This classification makes it possible to identify the census tracts that present a comparatively more unfavourable situation within the municipality.

Considerations for interpretation

The index represents a relative measure of vulnerability within Huércal-Overa. A low value does not imply an absence of vulnerability, but rather a more favourable situation with respect to the rest of the tracts analysed.

The indicators selected do not capture all the factors that may influence the response to heat. Aspects such as the state of health, the quality of housing, the availability of air conditioning, social support networks or proximity to health services are not incorporated owing to the lack of homogeneous information at the census scale.

Likewise, the weightings used respond to a methodological decision oriented towards prioritising physiological sensitivity and economic adaptation capacity. Therefore, the index should be interpreted as a tool for territorial comparison and prioritisation, not as an absolute measurement of individual vulnerability.

Results

The results obtained show that social vulnerability to heat presents an uneven distribution among the census tracts of Huércal-Overa. This variability responds to the combination of demographic, economic and educational factors, whose contribution differs between territories. The individual analysis of each indicator makes it possible to identify which dimension mainly conditions the vulnerability of each tract, while the combined index offers a synthetic view of the accumulation of unfavourable factors and facilitates territorial comparison within the municipality.

Distribution of age-related vulnerability

Age-related vulnerability showed relevant differences among the ten census tracts analysed. The

combined proportion of population aged 0 to 4 years and aged 65 years or over ranged between 15.58 % and 35.55 % of the total population.

Tract 0405304002 presented the highest age-related vulnerability, with 35.55 % of the population belonging to the age groups considered especially sensitive to heat. Next came tracts 0405304001, with 32.02 %, and 0405305002, with 30.32 %.

At the opposite extreme, the lowest proportions were recorded in tracts 0405303003, with 15.58 %, and 0405303002, with 15.99 %.

These results show an uneven distribution of the population most sensitive to heat and make it possible to identify the tracts in which the age structure may increase vulnerability to episodes of extreme temperatures.

Figure 39. Territorial distribution of age-related vulnerability in the census tracts of the urban core of Huércal-Overa.

Distribution of economic vulnerability

Economic vulnerability also presented important differences between the census tracts. The indicator used is normalised and inverted, so that the values closest to 1 correspond to the tracts with lower relative income and, therefore, with greater economic vulnerability.

Tract 0405301001 reached the maximum value of the indicator, with 1.0000, followed by 0405303002, with 0.9644. Tracts 0405304002, with 0.7901, and 0405302001, with 0.7645, also presented high values.

The comparatively more favourable economic conditions were identified in tract 0405303003, which obtained the minimum value of the indicator, followed by 0405302002, with 0.2832, and 0405303004, with 0.3974.

The distribution observed reveals that economic vulnerability does not necessarily coincide with age-related vulnerability. Some tracts present a relatively favourable demographic structure, but a lower potential economic capacity to face the effects of heat.

Figure 40. Territorial distribution of economic vulnerability in the census tracts of the urban core of Huércal-Overa.

Distribution of educational vulnerability

Educational vulnerability, calculated from the proportion of population aged 15 years or over with primary education or below, ranged between 16.05 % and 50.28 %.

Tract 0405304002 presented the highest value, with 50.28 % of the adult population in this educational category. It was followed by tracts 0405305002, with 35.94 %, and 0405301001, with 30.60 %.

The lowest values were recorded in 0405303003, with 16.05 %, followed by 0405302003, with 21.11 %, and 0405303004, with 21.93 %.

Tract 0405304002 therefore stands out for simultaneously presenting the highest age-related and educational vulnerability, in addition to a high economic vulnerability. This coincidence anticipates its prominent position in the combined index.

Figure 41. Territorial distribution of educational vulnerability in the census tracts of the urban core of Huércal-Overa.

Combined population vulnerability index

The integration of the three indicators made it possible to obtain a combined population vulnerability index for each census tract. The values ranged between 0 and 0.9265, revealing marked internal variability in the municipality.

Tract 0405304002 presented the highest value, with an index of 0.9265, and was the only one classified as very high vulnerability. This result responds to the coincidence of the highest age-related and educational vulnerability of the municipality with a high level of economic vulnerability.

Tracts 0405305002 and 0405304001 were classified as high vulnerability, with values of 0.6631 and 0.6512, respectively. Both present a high proportion of population sensitive by age, although their profiles differ in the contribution of income and educational level.

Three tracts were situated in the medium-vulnerability category: 0405301001, with an index of 0.5774; 0405302001, with 0.5357; and 0405303002, with 0.4064.

In these cases, vulnerability is especially conditioned by the economic dimension. Tracts 0405301001 and 0405303002 present the highest income-vulnerability values, although their age-related and educational indicators are more moderate.

Tracts 0405302003, 0405303004 and 0405302002 were classified as low vulnerability, with values of 0.2908, 0.2681 and 0.2515, respectively.

Finally, tract 0405303003 obtained an index of 0.0000 and was classified as very low vulnerability. This value does not represent an absolute absence of vulnerability, but rather indicates that this tract records the minimum municipal values in the three indicators after normalisation.

Table 8. Distribution of the vulnerability index by census tract.

Census tract	Vulnerability index	Classification
0405304002	0.9265	Very high
0405305002	0.6631	High
0405304001	0.6512	High
0405301001	0.5774	Medium
0405302001	0.5357	Medium
0405303002	0.4064	Medium
0405302003	0.2908	Low
0405303004	0.2681	Low
0405302002	0.2515	Low
0405303003	0.0000	Very low

Figure 42. Combined population vulnerability index by census tract of the urban core of Huércal-Overa.

Comparison between census tracts

The results show that social vulnerability is not distributed homogeneously in Huércal-Overa. Of the ten tracts analysed, one presents very high vulnerability, two high vulnerability, three medium vulnerability, three low vulnerability and one very low vulnerability.

Tract 0405304002 constitutes the socially most vulnerable area, since it concentrates high values in the three dimensions analysed. It is not, therefore, a vulnerability associated with a single factor, but rather an accumulation of demographic sensitivity, economic limitations and educational vulnerability.

Tracts 0405305002 and 0405304001 also present a high vulnerability, fundamentally conditioned

by their age structure. In 0405305002 a relatively high educational vulnerability is added, while in 0405304001 this component presents a lower weight.

Tracts 0405301001 and 0405303002 show a different profile. Their intermediate position in the index is determined mainly by their high economic vulnerability, which offsets comparatively more moderate age-related and educational values. This result highlights the usefulness of analysing the three dimensions jointly, since the index may reach relevant values through different social combinations.

For their part, the tracts classified as low vulnerability present relatively moderate values in the three dimensions, without a significant accumulation of unfavourable factors occurring.

Figure 43. Combined population vulnerability index by census tract of the complete municipality.

Synthesis of the results

The combined index reveals a marked territorial inequality of social vulnerability to heat in Huércal-Overa.

Tract 0405304002 stands out clearly above the rest, with a very high vulnerability derived from the coincidence of high values in age, income and education. Tracts 0405305002 and 0405304001 form a second level of social priority, both classified as high vulnerability.

The results also show that tracts with a similar overall level of vulnerability may present different profiles. In some cases, the sensitivity associated with age predominates, while in others the main limitation is related to economic capacity.

This differentiation is especially relevant for the subsequent design of adaptation measures. The actions should not respond solely to the final value of the index, but also to the dimension that explains the vulnerability of each tract.

The index obtained constitutes the social basis that will subsequently be integrated with thermal exposure and the rest of the territorial parameters. This integration will make it possible to determine whether the areas with greater population vulnerability also coincide with the sectors most exposed to heat and to establish a more complete territorial prioritisation.

CITIZEN PARTICIPATION AND COMMUNICATION

Citizen participation constitutes a key element in this project of analysis of the climate risk associated with urban heat in Huércal-Overa, as it makes it possible to complement the results obtained through climate and territorial analysis techniques with the knowledge, experience and perception of the population and of the different local actors.

The identification of zones especially exposed to heat, the understanding of certain territorial dynamics and the definition of possible adaptation strategies require the incorporation of local information that can hardly be obtained solely from statistical sources, cartography or spatial-analysis models. In this sense, participatory processes make it possible to enrich the technical diagnosis through the incorporation of territorial knowledge, everyday experiences and social perceptions linked to the effects of urban heat on the well-being and quality of life of the population.

With this purpose, a participation and communication process was developed, oriented towards incorporating local knowledge into the characterisation of climate risk, identifying zones perceived as especially affected by urban heat and fostering the awareness of citizens regarding the challenges associated with climate change and urban adaptation.

The process was structured through a combination of information, consultation and participation actions developed in collaboration with the City Council of Huércal-Overa. Among the main tools employed, the holding of a participatory session with municipal technical staff, the conduct of a citizen survey, the production of a participatory map of urban heat and the development of various communication and dissemination actions intended to facilitate the participation of citizens, associations, local entities and other relevant actors of the municipality stand out.

The results obtained through this process constitute a complementary source of socio-spatial information that makes it possible to contextualise and reinforce the results of the technical analysis, providing a view closer to the everyday reality of the municipality and incorporating factors of perception, use and experience of the territory that are essential for the correct characterisation of the climate risk associated with urban heat and for the identification of future priorities for action.

5.1. Participatory sessions with key actors of the municipality

With the aim of contrasting the results obtained during the diagnosis phase and incorporating specialised territorial knowledge into the analysis of the climate risk associated with urban heat, a participatory session aimed at the technical staff of the City Council of Huércal-Overa was developed.

The session was held online on 2 June 2025 and was attended by municipal technical staff linked to different areas of territorial management and urban planning. During the session, the main results obtained in the diagnosis phase were presented, including the analyses related to the evolution of heat waves, the spatial distribution of land surface temperature and the preliminary identification of urban areas potentially exposed to greater thermal risk.

The working dynamic was conceived as a space for continuous exchange between the project's technical team and the participants, favouring the validation of results and the incorporation of local knowledge. Likewise, a participatory dynamic supported by digital cartographic tools was developed, oriented towards identifying zones perceived as especially affected by urban heat and contrasting the results obtained during the diagnosis phase.

¿Cómo cambiarán las olas de calor?

	ACTUALIDAD	FUTURO
Días de ola de calor	10 días/año	RCP 4.5: 20 días/año RCP 8.5: más de 30 días/año
Duración de la ola	Menos o igual a 3 días	6 días de media en ambos escenarios
Frecuencia de la ola	2 olas/año	4-6 olas/año
Días de calor extremo	-	x2 días extremos

Figure 44. Example of the climate results presented and discussed during the participatory session with municipal technical staff.

Among the main contributions made by the participants, the following stand out:

- The influence of changes in agricultural and forest land uses on the current thermal conditions of the municipality.
- Identification of perceived thermal differences between different cores and hamlets, highlighting Las Labores, La Hoya and El Saltador.
- Designation of the surroundings of the Regional Hospital as one of the priority urban areas from the point of view of adaptation to heat.
- Municipal interest in promoting actions linked to urban green infrastructure, Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS) and Nature-based Solutions (NbS).
- Validation and local contextualisation of the heat patterns identified through the technical analysis.

The influence of the changes experienced in the agricultural and forest uses of the territory on the current thermal conditions. In this regard, the progressive replacement of certain tree crops by herbaceous crops was pointed out, as well as the disappearance of forest masses that historically contributed to moderating local temperatures. As concrete examples, the changes observed in zones such as El Saltador or the surroundings of the Watchtower of Huércal-Overa were mentioned.

Likewise, the participants identified perceived thermal differences between different cores of the municipality. Among the contributions made, the perception of more moderate temperatures in Las Labores compared with the main core of Huércal-Overa stands out, as well as a greater thermal sensation in areas such as La Hoya, associated with its geographical and territorial characteristics. These contributions made it possible to contextualise and validate some of the spatial patterns identified through the technical analysis, incorporating historical and territorial factors that help to explain part of the differences observed in the distribution of heat at the local scale.

During the session, comments were also made regarding possible urban spaces considered priorities from the point of view of climate adaptation. Among them, the surroundings of the Regional Hospital stand out, pointed out as one of the zones with the greatest problems associated with heat build-up and where future actions oriented towards improving thermal comfort, increasing the presence of vegetation and reinforcing the urban green infrastructure could be considered.

Finally, during the debate, the municipal interest in continuing to promote actions linked to urban green infrastructure was revealed, including projects currently planned related to the creation of

new green spaces, the incorporation of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS) and the application of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) as tools to improve the climate resilience of the municipality.

The contributions gathered during the session constitute a source of information of great value to complement the results obtained through the technical analysis, making it possible to incorporate historical, territorial and social factors that contribute to a better understanding of the urban-heat dynamics existing in Huércal-Overa. Likewise, they have made it possible to identify key elements for the interpretation of the results and to guide future lines of action linked to climate adaptation and the reinforcement of urban green infrastructure.

5.2. Citizen survey

With the aim of gathering the perception of the population about urban heat and the local priorities for climate adaptation, a voluntary citizen survey aimed at the population resident in Huércal-Overa was designed.

The survey was developed using a digital online-form tool, allowing simple and accessible participation from any device with an internet

connection. Its structure combines closed single- and multiple-choice questions, rating scales and open questions intended to gather observations, experiences and additional contributions from citizens.

Dissemination of the survey

The survey is available through an online form accessible via the following link:
<https://forms.gle/KirU9xjGoQdnjAoS8>

The tool will remain active during the next phase of the project in order to continue broadening citizen participation and enriching the information available on the local perception of urban heat and the priorities for climate adaptation.

The contents addressed include the perception of the evolution of temperatures in the municipality, the identification of zones with a greater thermal sensation, the habits of use of public space during periods of heat, the assessment of urban vegetation, the identification of vulnerable groups and the prioritisation of possible measures for adaptation to urban heat.

The dissemination of the survey was carried out through the project's microsite set up on the municipal website, as well as through the official

📍 ¿Dónde hace más calor en Huércal-Overa?

Hay calles, plazas y espacios donde el calor se nota más, especialmente en verano.

El Ayuntamiento está recopilando información para detectar estas zonas y localizar posibles espacios de mejora relacionados con sombra, vegetación y confort urbano.

👉 Participa aquí:

📄 Encuesta: <https://forms.gle/TDwyJ5S3f3w9hfw7>

Figure 45. Model text for the dissemination of the survey on the WhatsApp channel.

communication channels of the City Council, including WhatsApp, Facebook and Instagram. Additionally, access to the survey was facilitated by the incorporation of QR codes in the informational materials produced for the project.

Survey results

The results obtained show a widely shared perception of the increase in temperatures and in episodes of extreme heat in the municipality during recent years. 77.8 % of the participants consider that the heat has increased quite a lot or a great deal, while 55.6 % indicate that extreme heat greatly affects everyday life in Huércal-Overa and 28.9 % consider that it affects it quite a lot.

Likewise, there is a high consensus regarding the spatial distribution of heat in the municipality. 88.9 % of those surveyed consider that there are zones where heat is clearly perceived with greater intensity than in others, which reinforces the relevance of incorporating participatory tools

that make it possible to identify and characterise those spaces from the everyday experience of the population.

As regards the most problematic urban typologies, streets without trees stand out clearly as the spaces where a greater build-up of heat is perceived, being pointed out by more than 90 % of the participants. Urban squares, school surroundings, car parks and other spaces with scarce plant cover and a high presence of paved surfaces also appear recurrently. The open observations made by the participants repeatedly highlight the lack of shade, the reduction of urban vegetation and the need to increase the presence of trees in streets and public spaces.

Regarding the most affected groups, the responses recurrently identify older people, children, people with chronic illnesses and workers exposed to the open air, coinciding with the groups usually considered most vulnerable to episodes of extreme heat.

En verano, ¿diría que el calor en Huércal-Overa ha aumentado en los últimos años?
45 respuestas

¿En qué medida cree que el calor extremo afecta a la vida diaria en el municipio?
45 respuestas

Figure 46. Citizen perception of the evolution of temperatures in Huércal-Overa and of the impact of extreme heat on everyday life.

Figure 47. Typologies of urban spaces where citizens perceive a greater build-up of heat.

The open questions included in the survey have made it possible to identify specific spaces of the municipality perceived as especially affected by urban heat. Among the locations mentioned most frequently, the Plaza Mayor, the Carretera de la Estación, the fairground, the Plaza de la Constitución, the surroundings of the Hospital de la Inmaculada, the Noria del Pino, the Alameda and various school surroundings stand out. In general, the zones indicated share characteristics associated with high solar exposure, scarcity of shade and a limited presence of vegetation.

Likewise, the participants have identified as priorities those urban spaces with a high influx of population or a special social and functional relevance, highlighting public squares, health facilities, educational centres, car parks and the main road axes of the municipality. These contributions make it possible to complement the technical analysis through the incorporation of local knowledge about spaces that generate situations of thermal discomfort recurrently perceived by citizens.

The open responses also made it possible to identify certain urban spaces recurrently mentioned by citizens as especially affected by urban heat.

In relation to the adaptation measures, the solutions linked to urban green infrastructure are those that receive the most positive assessment. Among the most supported actions, the planting of trees in streets and public spaces, the generation of natural shade, the expansion and improvement of parks and green areas, the incorporation of vegetation in squares and urban spaces and the creation of new green areas on vacant plots stand out.

The open responses also show a recurrent demand for an increase in urban trees, the generation of shade in streets and squares, the improvement of parks and public spaces and the adaptation of school and health environments. Some contributions highlight the need to reinforce the continuity of shaded pedestrian routes and to prioritise actions in those spaces that present high solar exposure during the summer months.

Table 9. Spaces identified by citizens as especially affected by urban heat.

Space identified	Frequency of mention
Plaza Mayor	High
Carretera de la Estación	High
Recinto Ferial	High
Hospital de la Inmaculada	High
Plaza de la Constitución	Medium
Noria del Pino	Medium
Alameda	Medium
School surroundings	Medium

Las soluciones basadas en la naturaleza son intervenciones que utilizan elementos naturales, como la vegetación o el agua, para reducir el calor en las ciudades y mejorar el bienestar de las personas.

Figure 48. Measures for adaptation to urban heat considered priorities by citizens.

These results show a high social acceptance of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) as a tool to improve thermal comfort and reinforce the climate adaptation of the municipality.

Overall, the results obtained constitute a complementary source of information of great usefulness for contextualising the technical analysis developed in the project, making it possible to incorporate the citizen perception of the impacts of urban heat, the priority areas for action and the adaptation measures considered most necessary by the population. The coincidence observed between many of the locations indicated by citizens and the areas identified through the technical analyses reinforces the validity of the results obtained and reveals the value of local knowledge for the characterisation of the climate risk associated with urban heat.

5.3. Participatory map of urban heat

With the aim of complementing the results obtained through the analysis of land surface temperature (LST) and gathering the local perception of the thermal dynamics of the municipality, an online participatory map of urban heat aimed at citizens and the different local actors was set up.

The tool allows participants to identify on a georeferenced grid those zones where they perceive a greater build-up of heat or worse thermal-comfort conditions during the summer periods. Likewi-

se, the map facilitates the identification of spaces perceived as especially problematic, possible thermal shelters and priority areas for the improvement of shade, vegetation and urban comfort.

The contributions recorded make it possible to generate a complementary layer of information based on the everyday experience of the population and the different local actors, incorporating perceptual and social variables that cannot be obtained solely through spatial-analysis techniques.

The participatory map has recorded a total of 55 citizen contributions distributed mainly throughout the urban core of Huércal-Overa. The contributions are concentrated especially in certain urban axes, squares, public spaces and facility surroundings where citizens perceive a greater build-up of heat and worse thermal-comfort conditions during the summer months.

The spatial patterns observed show a significant concentration of contributions in the central axis of the municipality, including areas close to the Plaza Mayor, the Carretera de la Estación, the surroundings of the Hospital de la Inmaculada, various urban squares and other spaces characterised by a high presence of paved surfaces, a limited plant cover and a reduced availability of shade.

2. Mapa de Calor Participativo

Aquí puedes señalar las zonas donde percibes más calor, votando sobre una cuadrícula, incluyendo también pedanías.

Figure 49. Interface of the participatory map of urban heat on the municipal microsite.

Figure 50. Example of the georeferenced grid used for collecting the citizen contributions in different cores

Figure 51. Spatial distribution of the contributions recorded on the participatory map of urban heat.

The zones identified through the participatory map present notable consistency with the locations indicated by citizens in the open questions of the survey, reinforcing the consistency of the results obtained through both participatory tools. This coincidence is especially relevant in spaces widely used by the population, where the perception of thermal discomfort appears to be more consolidated.

Likewise, the results show a general correspondence with some of the patterns identified through the technical analysis of land surface temperature (LST), particularly in urban areas with high soil sealing and a lower presence of vegetation. This convergence between technical analysis and citizen perception reinforces the validity of the zones identified as priorities from the point of view of adaptation to urban heat.

It should be noted that practically all the contributions recorded have been associated with high levels of thermal perception, so the main interpretative value of the tool lies in the spatial location of the points indicated rather than in the differentiation of the perceived intensity. In this sense, the map makes it possible to effectively identify those spaces where citizens perceive a greater build-up of heat and where future actions oriented towards improving urban thermal comfort could be prioritised.

The results obtained reveal the usefulness of participatory cartographic tools for complementing the technical analysis, incorporating local knowledge and facilitating the identification of priority areas for action against the climate risk associated with urban heat. The coincidence observed between the zones identified on the participatory map, the locations indicated in the citizen survey and the contributions made during the municipal technical session provides a solid basis for the subsequent prioritisation of climate-adaptation actions in the municipality.

5.4. Communication actions

With the aim of making the project known among citizens, facilitating access to the information generated and fostering participation in the different tools set up, a communication and dissemination strategy was developed in coordination with the City Council of Huércal-Overa.

The main communication tool was the creation of a specific microsite within the municipal website, conceived as a centralising space for all the information related to the project. This platform incorporates a general description of the initiative, the main results obtained during the diagnosis phase, informational documentation and direct access to the different citizen-participation tools developed within the framework of the project.

<https://www.huercal-overa.es/Servicios/cmsdi-pro/index.nsf/informacion.xsp?p=huercal-overa&documentId=4CE343CFC5F09785C1258D-F700231F5D>

As support for the dissemination actions, an informational One Pager document was produced with summarised information on the objectives of the project, the main results obtained and the different participation channels set up. This material incorporates QR codes that allow direct access to the municipal microsite, the citizen survey and the participatory map of urban heat, facilitating citizens' access to the different tools developed.

The dissemination of the project was carried out continuously through the official communication channels of the City Council of Huércal-Overa, including the municipal website, the institutional WhatsApp channel and the official profiles on Facebook and Instagram. Throughout the process, various communications adapted to the degree of progress of the project were developed, including the initial presentation of the initiative, the dissemination of the first results obtained during the diagnosis phase, the promotion of the citizen-participation tools and a final communication oriented towards reinforcing participation during the last weeks of information collection.

The publications made it possible to inform citizens about the objectives and progress of the project, facilitate access to the results obtained and foster the active participation of the population in the citizen survey and in the participatory map of urban heat. Likewise, the interactions recorded on social media reflect the interest of citizens in the issues related to urban heat, thermal comfort and adaptation to climate change, contributing to generating a space for exchange and awareness around this problem.

PROYECTO LUGIA

ANÁLISIS DEL RIESGO DE LAS OLAS DE CALOR Y SU IMPACTO EN GRUPOS VULNERABLES

EL RIESGO CLIMÁTICO NO SOLO TIENE QUE VER CON EL CALOR, TAMBIÉN CON LA VULNERABILIDAD Y LA FALTA DE VEGETACIÓN

EL CLIMA ESTÁ CAMBIANDO

- La temperatura media ha aumentado en más de 1°C en los últimos 50 años.
- Se prevén hasta 6 veces más días de ola de calor anuales.
- 114 días cálidos en 2022 frente a una media de 35 a 45 en los últimos 50 años.

El municipio avanza hacia un escenario más cálido y seco.

¿POR QUÉ OCURRE? LA CIUDAD ACUMULA CALOR

- Hay poca vegetación y falta de sombra natural.
- El asfalto y las superficies duras acumulan calor.
- El calor se acumula durante el día, generando olas de calor nocturnas.

Solo un 7% del municipio tiene sombra natural.

¿A QUIÉN AFECTA? EL CALOR NOS AFECTA A TODOS, PERO NO LO SUFRIMOS DE LA MISMA MANERA

Hay personas más vulnerables:

- Personas mayores.
- Niños y niñas.
- Personas que trabajan al aire libre.
- Personas en situación de dependencia.

El calor tiene un impacto directo en la salud y el bienestar.

¿DÓNDE OCURRE? HAY ZONAS MÁS EXPUESTAS

El calor se concentra en el núcleo urbano de Huércal-Overa, especialmente en la zona norte, que incluye el barrio de la Molineta y el área del Hospital de la Inmaculada.

¿QUÉ PODEMOS HACER? SOLUCIONES BASADAS EN LA NATURALEZA

Acciones que utilizan vegetación y elementos naturales para reducir el calor:

- Más árboles en calles y plazas.
- Más zonas verdes.
- Incorporación de agua (fontes, etc.).
- Reducción de superficies duras.

Mejoran el confort térmico y la calidad de vida.

PROYECCIONES FUTURAS ¿QUÉ SE CONSEGUIRÁ A LARGO PLAZO?

- Reducir el impacto del calor en el espacio urbano.
- Mejorar el confort térmico en calles y plazas.
- Incorporar más naturaleza en la ciudad.

Avanzar hacia un municipio más saludable y resiliente.

TU PARTICIPACIÓN ES CLAVE

Encuesta
Sesiones
Mapas participativos

¡PARTICIPA Y FORMA PARTE DEL CAMBIO!

Entre todos podemos construir un municipio más adaptado, más saludable y habitable.

Figure 52. Informational document (One Pager) produced for the dissemination of the project and the promotion of the citizen-participation tools.

¿DÓNDE HACE MÁS CALOR EN HUÉRCAL-OVERA?

Ayúdanos a identificar las zonas más calurosas y los espacios donde mejorar nuestro entorno urbano.

ENCUESTA ONLINE
Cuéntanos tu percepción sobre el calor en tu barrio.

MAPAS PARTICIPATIVOS
Señala en el mapa las zonas más calurosas y posibles mejoras.

SESIÓN ABIERTA A LA CIUDADANÍA
28 DE MAYO

¡ÚLTIMOS DÍAS PARA PARTICIPAR!

El proyecto de adaptación al calor urbano de Huércal-Overa entra en su fase final.

Ayúdanos a identificar las zonas con más calor y los espacios de oportunidad para hacer nuestro municipio más confortable y resiliente.

¡Tu opinión aún cuenta!
PARTICIPA

Figure 53. Example of graphic material produced to graphically support the communications through Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp.

Figure 54. Example of communications shared through the City Council's official Facebook channel to report on the project, present preliminary results and promote citizen participation.

Figure 55. Example of communications shared through the City Council's official Instagram channel to report on the project, present preliminary results and promote citizen participation.

In a complementary manner, direct communication actions were developed with different actors and groups of the municipality, including neighbourhood associations, associations of older people, social entities, associations linked to the field of health, groups of people with disabilities and educational centres. These actions had the purpose of broadening the reach of the participatory process, favouring the incorporation of diverse perspectives and reinforcing the participation of groups especially relevant for the analysis of the climate risk associated with urban heat.

The set of actions developed has made it possible to increase the visibility of the project, facilitate citizens' access to the information generated and promote the participation of the different local actors in the process of analysis of and adaptation to urban heat. The information obtained through these actions constitutes a complementary element of great usefulness for contextualising the technical results and reinforcing the integration of the social dimension into the characterisation of municipal climate risk.

Estimado equipo del Colegio Virgen del Río,

Nos ponemos en contacto con ustedes en relación con el proyecto que se está desarrollando para el Ayuntamiento de Huércal-Overa con el objetivo de analizar los efectos del calor urbano en el municipio e identificar posibles medidas de adaptación que contribuyan a mejorar el confort térmico y la calidad de vida de la población.

Consideramos especialmente importante contar con la participación de los centros educativos, ya que los espacios escolares desempeñan un papel fundamental en el bienestar cotidiano de niños, niñas y jóvenes, especialmente durante los periodos de altas temperaturas. Por este motivo, nos gustaría especialmente conocer la percepción y experiencia de la comunidad educativa, así como contar con su colaboración para identificar posibles problemáticas y oportunidades de mejora relacionadas con el calor urbano en el municipio.

Nos gustaría invitar al centro a participar en este proceso a través de:

- Una encuesta ciudadana sobre percepción del calor urbano.
- Un mapa participativo para identificar las zonas donde se percibe una mayor acumulación de calor.
- Un mapa de espacios de oportunidad para proponer posibles actuaciones de mejora relacionadas con la sombra, la vegetación o la adaptación climática.

Adjunto remitimos un documento informativo del proyecto. Asimismo, pueden acceder a toda la información a través de los siguientes enlaces:

🔗 Web oficial del proyecto y mapas: <https://www.huercal-overa.es/Servicios/cmsdipro/index.nsf/informacion.xsp?p=huercal-overa&documentId=4CE343CFC5F09785C1258DF700231F5D>

Figure 56. Example of a dissemination email addressed to local associations and entities.

INTEGRATION OF LOCAL PARAMETERS FOR THE CHARACTERISATION OF CLIMATE RISK

The characterisation of the climate risk associated with urban heat in Huércal-Overa was developed by integrating the various analyses carried out throughout the study. This approach integrates the information relating to thermal exposure, the distribution and characteristics of the Urban Green Infrastructure, its environmental regulation capacity, the social vulnerability of the population and the local knowledge obtained through the participatory process.

Climate risk is therefore understood as the result of the interaction between the intensity of the thermal hazard, the degree of exposure of the population and the urban environment, and the vulnerability conditions that may increase or reduce the capacity to respond to extreme heat episodes. From this perspective, an area with high temperatures does not necessarily present the highest level of risk if it has adequate plant cover, shaded spaces, a less vulnerable population or a greater adaptive capacity. Likewise, areas with moderate thermal exposure may acquire priority relevance when they concentrate particularly sensitive population or present significant deficits in green infrastructure and thermal comfort.

The results obtained show that climate risk is not distributed homogeneously across the municipality. There are relevant differences between the various districts and urban centres in terms of surface temperatures, availability and condition of vegetation, presence of shade, characteristics of the urban fabric and sociodemographic vulnerability. The integration of these variables makes it possible to identify the spaces in which unfavourable environmental conditions, a lower thermal regulation capacity and a greater vulnerability of the population coincide.

This integrated view makes it possible to move beyond an interpretation of risk based exclusively on temperature and to advance towards a more complete understanding of the factors that condition the impacts of urban heat. The integration of environmental, social and territorial variables provides a more solid basis for establishing action priorities and guiding future climate adaptation measures, especially those related to urban naturalisation, the increase of shade and the improvement of the thermal regulation capacity of public space.

6.1. Analysis by district of the environmental risk associated with urban heat

Methodology

Environmental variables considered

The analysis of the environmental risk associated with urban heat was carried out by integrating three parameters directly related to thermal exposure and to the capacity of the urban environment to attenuate its effects: tree cover, land surface temperature and total shade. The combination of these variables made it possible to generate a synthetic environmental index for each census tract of the urban centre of Huércal-Overa.

Land surface temperature, or LST, was incorporated as a direct variable of thermal exposure, so that the highest values were associated with more unfavourable environmental conditions. Conversely, tree cover and total shade were considered variables of thermal protection and regulation, owing to their capacity to reduce incident radiation, generate shade and moderate the temperatures of the urban environment.

Homogenisation of the parameters

Before integrating the three variables, their values were homogenised on a common scale, so that they could be compared and combined despite presenting different units of measurement and ranges of variation.

Likewise, the direction of the indicators was adjusted so that the highest values of the final index would always represent a greater environmental unfavourability in the face of heat. In the case of LST, the highest surface temperatures received the highest risk values. In the case of tree cover and total shade, the values were transformed to represent their deficit, so that a lower availability of vegetation or shade was associated with a higher level of environmental risk.

Weighting and integration of the variables

The three variables were integrated by means of a weighted sum, assigning each one a specific weight according to its relevance within the analysis. Tree cover received a weighting of 40 %, total shade 35 % and land surface temperature 25 %.

The environmental thermal risk index was calculated according to the following expression:

$$\text{ENVIRONMENTAL THERMAL RISK INDEX} = 0.40 \times \text{TREE COVER DEFICIT} + 0.35 \times \text{TOTAL SHADE DEFICIT} + 0.25 \times \text{NORMALISED LST}$$

The greater weighting assigned to tree cover responds to its structural and sustained contribution to urban thermal regulation, both through the generation of shade and through evapotranspiration processes. Total shade also received a high weight, as it directly represents the protection against solar radiation available in urban space. For its part, LST was incorporated as an indicator of the thermal response of surfaces and of the spatial intensity of warming.

Aggregation of the results by census tract

Once the environmental index had been calculated, the values were aggregated by census tract to obtain a homogeneous territorial representation of the environmental risk associated with urban heat.

The resulting map makes it possible to compare the different census tracts and to identify those in which high surface temperatures, insufficient tree cover and a reduced availability of shade coincide. In this way, the index synthesises in a single value the main environmental conditions that may increase the exposure of the population to heat.

Results

Analysis of the main centre of Huércal-Overa

The map of environmental risk associated with urban heat shows a heterogeneous territorial distribution across the seven districts analysed. The integration of tree cover, total shade and land surface temperature makes it possible to differentiate sectors with low, moderate and high risk levels.

The high environmental risk level is concentrated in the northern sector of the urban centre, corresponding to District 4 (0405302003). This unit presents the most unfavourable environmental conditions within the area analysed, as a result of the weighted combination of a lower thermal regulation capacity associated with vegetation and shade, together with a more unfavourable surface thermal behaviour.

The low environmental risk levels are located in the central and central-western areas of the urban centre. Specifically, this category corresponds to District 3 (0405302002) and District 7 (0405303004). In these units, the interaction between tree cover, shade and surface temperature generates comparatively more favourable conditions in the face of urban heat.

The remaining units present a moderate environmental risk level. This category includes District 1 (0405301001), located at the southern end; District 2 (0405302001), located immediately to the north of the former; District 5 (0405303002), in the central-eastern sector; and District 6 (0405303003), which occupies a large part of the eastern area of the urban centre.

Overall, the results show a defined spatial pattern, characterised by a greater environmental risk in the northern sector, more favourable conditions in part of the central area and an intermediate situation in the southern and eastern sectors. This

distribution shows that environmental exposure to heat and the thermal regulation capacity of the urban environment are not homogeneous across the different districts.

The resulting classification represents exclusively the environmental dimension of the analysis. Therefore, a district with a high environmental risk will not necessarily present the highest final climate vulnerability, since this will also depend on the sociodemographic characteristics of the population.

Results of the environmental risk in the hamlets

The analysis of the environmental risk associated with urban heat in the hamlets shows a relatively homogeneous distribution. Of the six urban centres considered, five present a moderate environmental risk level, while only Las Labores reaches the high risk category. No hamlets classified with a low environmental risk level are identified.

El Salvador, La Hoya, San Francisco, Santa María de Nieva and Úrcal present a moderate environmental risk level. This classification indicates that the weighted integration of tree cover, total shade and land surface temperature gives rise to intermediate conditions in the face of urban heat. Although these centres do not present the most unfavourable values of the index, neither do they reach conditions sufficiently favourable to be classified in the low risk category.

The common classification of these five hamlets does not imply that they present equivalent values in each of the parameters analysed. On the contrary, the moderate result may respond to different combinations of tree cover, shade availability and surface temperature. Thus, a greater presence of vegetation in one hamlet may be offset by an insufficient availability of effective shade or by higher surface temperatures, while in other centres moderate deficits may concur in the three indicators.

Figure 57. Environmental risk map of the urban centre of Huércal-Overa

Figure 58. Environmental risk map of the main hamlets.

Las Labores constitutes the main exception, presenting a high environmental risk level. This result indicates that the combination of the parameters considered generates comparatively more unfavourable conditions in the face of heat than in the rest of the hamlets. Consequently, Las Labores is configured as the priority centre within this group from a strictly environmental perspective.

In general terms, the results show that the hamlets present a limited regulation capacity in the face of urban heat. The absence of units classified with low risk shows that, even in those centres with a relevant presence of vegetation, deficits persist related to effective tree cover, shade availability or the thermal behaviour of surfaces.

This classification represents exclusively the environmental dimension of the analysis. To determine the final climate vulnerability of each hamlet, the results must be interpreted jointly with the social and demographic characteristics of their population. In this way, a moderate environmental risk may acquire greater relevance when it coincides with a high concentration of sensitive population, while the high risk identified in Las Labores will have to be assessed taking into account its population vulnerability as well.

6.2. Integration of social parameters for the analysis of climate vulnerability

Methodology

The characterisation of climate vulnerability in the face of urban heat requires considering not only the environmental conditions of the territory, but also the characteristics of the exposed population.

The same level of environmental risk may generate different impacts depending on the presence of particularly sensitive groups, the concentration of population and the social response capacity. For this reason, the analysis integrates the environmental dimension and the social dimension, making it possible to identify the areas in which exposure to heat coincides with greater population vulnerability.

Integrated components

To incorporate the social dimension into the analysis of the climate risk associated with urban heat, two main components were combined: the environmental risk map and the population vulnerability index.

The environmental risk map synthesises the information relating to tree cover, total shade and land surface temperature. For its part, the population vulnerability index represents the social sensitivity to heat on the basis of the demographic indicators previously analysed.

The integration of both components makes it possible to relate the physical and environmental conditions of the urban environment with the characteristics of the exposed population and to identify the areas in which unfavourable environmental conditions and greater social vulnerability coincide.

Territorial aggregation and determination of climate vulnerability

To ensure the spatial correspondence between both sources of information, the data were aggregated using the same territorial units. In the urban centre of Huércal-Overa, the information was integrated by districts, corresponding to the census tracts included in the study. In the case of the hamlets, each urban centre was treated as an independent territorial unit.

Once the scale of analysis had been homogenised, the categories of the environmental risk map were cross-referenced with the values of the population vulnerability index. The result made it possible to assign each district and hamlet a relative level of climate vulnerability in the face of urban heat.

In this way, climate vulnerability is interpreted as the result of the concurrence between the environmental conditions of the territory and the degree of sensitivity of the population. The units in which a high environmental risk and a greater population vulnerability coincide therefore acquire a greater priority for the planning of adaptation measures.

Results

Results of the socio-environmental risk in the urban centre of Huércal-Overa

The integration of the environmental risk with the population vulnerability index shows a differentiated territorial distribution of the socio-environmental risk in the urban centre of Huércal-Overa.

The results make it possible to classify the seven districts analysed into low, medium and high risk levels, according to the concurrence between more or less unfavourable environmental conditions and the degree of vulnerability of the resident population.

The high socio-environmental risk level is concentrated in District 1 (0405301001), located at the southern end of the urban centre. This unit constitutes the most unfavourable area of the integrated analysis, combining moderate-risk environmental conditions with a comparatively high population vulnerability. The result shows that an intermediate environmental situation may acquire priority relevance when it coincides with a more sensitive population or with a lower adaptive capacity in the face of heat.

The medium risk level is recorded in District 2 (0405302001), District 4 (0405302003) and District 6 (0405303003). In these areas, the combination of environmental risk and population vulnerability generates an intermediate situation. However, the origin of this classification is not necessarily the same in all cases. In District 4, the result is conditioned by a high environmental risk, while in districts 2 and 6 the combination between moderate environmental conditions and the social vulnerability of the population intervenes.

Conversely, District 3 (0405302002), District 5 (0405303002) and District 7 (0405303004) present a low socio-environmental risk level. In these units, the cross-referencing between the environmental and social parameters gives rise to a comparatively more favourable situation. This may respond to better conditions of tree cover, shade and thermal behaviour, to a lower population vulnerability or to the combination of both factors.

The comparison with the environmental risk map shows the importance of incorporating the social dimension. District 4, which presented the highest environmental risk level, moves to a medium socio-environmental category when the characteristics of its population are integrated. Conversely, District 1, initially classified with a moderate environmental risk, reaches the high socio-environmental level owing to the weight of population vulnerability.

Figure 59. Socio-environmental risk map of the urban centre of Huércal-Overa.

Overall, the results show that the climate risk in the face of heat does not depend solely on thermal intensity or on the availability of vegetation and shade. The incorporation of social factors modifies the territorial hierarchy and makes it possible to identify District 1 as a priority area, where the concurrence between the environmental conditions and the vulnerability of the population may increase the potential impacts of extreme heat episodes.

Results of the socio-environmental risk in the hamlets

The integration of the environmental risk with the population vulnerability index substantially modifies the classification previously obtained for the hamlets. The six urban centres analysed present a high socio-environmental risk level.

This result indicates that, although the strictly environmental analysis classified most of the

hamlets at a moderate level, the incorporation of the social and demographic characteristics of the population increases their final risk level. Population vulnerability therefore acts as a determining factor in the integrated assessment of the potential impacts of heat.

In El Saltador, La Hoya, San Francisco, Santa María de Nieva and Úrcal, the moderate environmental risk is combined with a population vulnerability sufficiently high to place these centres in the high socio-environmental category. This shows that intermediate environmental conditions do not necessarily imply a reduced climate risk when there is a significant presence of sensitive population or a lower capacity to respond to extreme heat episodes.

Las Labores maintains the high risk category that it already presented in the environmental analysis. In this case, the concurrence of particularly unfavourable environmental conditions and a high

Figure 60. Socio-environmental risk map of the main hamlets.

population vulnerability reinforces its priority character within the set of hamlets studied.

The homogeneity of the final classification does not imply that all the hamlets present the same values in the environmental or social parameters. The high level may respond to different combinations of thermal exposure, tree cover deficit, shade availability and characteristics of the population. However, the integrated result indicates that in all the centres there is a sufficiently significant concurrence of environmental and social factors to justify priority attention.

Overall, the results show that the incorporation of the social dimension decisively alters the territorial hierarchy obtained from the environmental parameters. While the environmental risk map showed a mostly moderate situation, the socio-environmental analysis identifies all the hamlets as high-risk areas in the face of urban heat. This pattern reinforces the need to direct adaptation measures not only towards the improvement of plant cover and shade, but also towards the protection of the most vulnerable population.

6.3. Integration of participatory information in the characterisation of risk

The information obtained through the participatory process was incorporated as a complementary validation tool to contrast, interpret and territorially refine the results of the environmental and socio-environmental analyses. Unlike the quantitative indices, calculated by aggregating variables by districts and hamlets, the participatory map made it possible to capture the everyday experience of citizens regarding specific spaces in which a greater accumulation of heat or deficient thermal comfort conditions are perceived.

The participatory map recorded a total of 55 contributions, distributed along the central axis of the urban centre of Huércal-Overa. The most relevant concentrations were located in areas close to the Plaza Mayor, the Carretera de la Estación, the surroundings of the Hospital de la Inmaculada, various squares and other public spaces and facilities of everyday use. In general, these are areas with a significant presence of paved surfaces, a limited availability of shade and a lower plant cover.

No contributions were recorded in the hamlets analysed. For this reason, the participatory information does not make it possible to directly validate or qualify the environmental and socio-environmental risk results obtained for El Saltador, La Hoya, Las Labores, San Francisco, Santa María de Nieva and Úrcal. The absence of observations should not be interpreted as an absence of thermal comfort problems, but rather as a limitation of the territorial coverage achieved by the participatory process.

Coincidence with the environmental risk map

The distribution of the contributions shows a significant correspondence with several of the areas identified by means of the environmental risk map. In the northern sector, the concentration of observations in the surroundings of the Hospital de la Inmaculada and its access points spatially coincides with District 4 (0405302003), classified with a high environmental risk level. This coincidence reinforces the identification of the north of the urban centre as one of the areas with the most unfavourable conditions in the face of heat.

Contributions are also recorded in the central and southern sectors, corresponding mainly to districts with moderate environmental risk, such as districts 1 (0405301001), 2 (0405302001) and 6 (0405303003). In these areas, citizen perception confirms that an intermediate environmental risk classification at the district scale may include specific spaces with relevant deficits of shade, vegetation or thermal comfort.

However, the participatory map also gathers observations within central areas classified with low environmental risk, especially in sectors belonging to districts 3 (0405302002) and 7 (0405303004). This circumstance does not constitute a contradiction between the two analyses. The environmental index represents the aggregate value of

the whole of each district, while citizens identify specific streets, squares, routes and gathering spaces. Therefore, within a district with a globally favourable situation, localised points of high solar exposure or thermal discomfort may exist.

Coincidence with the socio-environmental risk map

The correspondence is particularly relevant when comparing the contributions with the socio-environmental risk map. In the southern sector, the presence of observations along the urban axis coincides with District 1 (0405301001), identified as the only unit with a high socio-environmental risk. This coincidence reinforces its consideration as a priority area, since to the population vulnerability and the environmental conditions is added an effective citizen perception of thermal discomfort in everyday spaces.

In the north, the contributions recorded around the Hospital de la Inmaculada and other facilities coincide with District 4 (0405302003), classified with a medium socio-environmental risk. Likewise, the continuity of observations along the central axis affects sectors belonging to districts 2 (0405302001) and 6 (0405303003), also classified with medium risk. Although these units do not reach the maximum level of the integrated index, the presence of spaces frequently flagged by citizens increases their functional relevance and advises considering them in the prioritisation of actions.

The contributions located in districts 3 (0405302002), 5 (0405303002) and 7 (0405303004), classified with a low socio-environmental risk, once again show the difference between the aggregate scale of the index and the specific scale of citizen experience. These results make it possible to detect problematic micro-areas that would remain hidden when working exclusively with average values by census tract.

Integrated interpretation

Overall, the participatory information confirms the main territorial patterns identified by means of the technical analyses in the urban centre of Huércal-Overa, especially the relevance of the northern and southern sectors and of the central urban axis. The coincidence with District 4 in the north and with District 1 in the south provides additional validation of their importance within the climate diagnosis.

At the same time, participation introduces a spatial and functional precision that the aggregate indices cannot provide. The contributions not only indicate where unfavourable environmental conditions exist, but also where these affect squares, pedestrian itineraries, facilities and public spaces used regularly by the population.

Therefore, the participatory map should not be interpreted as an additional index nor as a substitute for the environmental and socio-environmental risk maps. Its main function consists in contrasting and complementing the patterns identified by means of the technical analysis, locating critical points within the various districts and incorporating information on the everyday use and citizen perception of thermal comfort in public space. This function is limited to the main urban centre, since the absence of contributions in the hamlets prevents an equivalent comparison between citizen perception and the technical results.

CONCLUSIONS

This report has made it possible to move from the general climate diagnosis developed in the previous phase of the project towards a more local, integrated and operational characterisation of the risk associated with urban heat in Huércal-Overa. This second phase is not limited to confirming the growing exposure of the municipality to heat waves, but rather delves into the urban, environmental, vegetation-related, social and participatory factors that condition the way in which this risk manifests itself across the territory and affects the population.

The results obtained confirm that Huércal-Overa is facing a scenario of progressive intensification of extreme heat, consistent with the climate trends previously identified. The increase in the frequency, duration and intensity of heat waves constitutes a relevant threat to public health, urban habitability, the functionality of public space and the management of municipal resources. However, the analysis developed shows that climate risk does not depend solely on the evolution of temperatures, but also on the physical configuration of the territory, the characteristics of urban surfaces, the availability and functionality of vegetation, the thermal regulation capacity of green spaces, the vulnerability of the population and the way in which citizens use and perceive urban space.

The main contribution of this phase therefore consists in translating a climate threat of a general nature into a territorial reading capable of differentiating between thermally unfavourable areas, areas with a lower environmental regulation capacity and spaces where these conditions also coincide with a greater population vulnerability. This integrated interpretation provides a more precise basis for identifying priorities and guiding future climate adaptation actions.

Urban configuration conditions exposure to heat, but its effects depend on the territorial context

The results show that the thermal behaviour of Huércal-Overa is closely related to the configuration and use of the territory. Dry agricultural surfaces, open spaces, mobility areas and peripheral sectors present a greater propensity to surface warming, while green and recreational spaces and certain residential and facility areas show relatively more moderate conditions.

This relationship does not respond solely to the type of material present. The function of the land, its degree of exposure, the presence of moisture, vegetation and urban configuration explain the thermal differences better than a classification based exclusively on broad cover categories. This implies that adaptation cannot rely on uniform solutions, but must respond to the specific combination of uses, materials and territorial conditions of each space.

The distribution of heat also presents a persistent spatial structure. The warm and cool areas tend to cluster, which shows that these are not isolated anomalies but rather patterns related to the organisation of the municipality. The agricultural and peripheral sectors of the north and east concentrate the most unfavourable conditions, while certain areas of the centre-south present a greater thermal moderation capacity.

The shade analysis introduces a fundamental nuance: an area does not need to record the highest surface temperature to present significant discomfort conditions. The absence of protection against direct solar radiation can significantly increase the exposure of pedestrians and users of public space. For this reason, shade must be considered a basic urban infrastructure and not a complementary element of design.

The study of pavements reinforces this interpretation. The territorial predominance of asphalt, together with its high solar absorption capacity, makes this surface one of the main potential factors of heat accumulation. Its influence does not derive solely from its radiative properties, but also from its enormous extent within the road system. Actions on pavements will therefore be more effective when combined with shade, permeability, reduction of exposed surfaces and redesign of public space.

The thermal regulation provided by Green Infrastructure depends on its structure, continuity and resilience

The inventory developed shows that the quantity of vegetation, considered in isolation, does not make it possible to adequately assess the functionality of the Urban Green Infrastructure. The richness of species, the number of specimens or the total green area must be interpreted jointly with the canopy cover, the spatial continuity, the size, the physiological condition and the location of the vegetation.

Huércal-Overa presents a significant plant diversity, but this richness coexists with a limited and unevenly distributed territorial cover. Some districts have a relatively diverse composition, while others present clear cover deficits and a lower potential capacity to provide shade and thermal regulation.

In the hamlets, a greater presence of vegetation does not necessarily imply a more resilient or functional green infrastructure. In several centres, the cover is associated with a strong dominance of a single species or with formations related to agricultural uses. These structures may provide plant surface, but they do not in themselves guarantee diversity, urban continuity or a homogeneous provision of ecosystem services.

The comparison between surface temperature and green areas shows that the average cooling effect is reduced when the set of spaces is analysed. However, this result does not question the role of vegetation, but rather shows the limitations of a fragmented green infrastructure, of small size or integrated into highly sealed environments.

The tree cover maps confirm that continuous and dense vegetation masses are more frequently associated with moderate surface temperatures. Conversely, isolated trees and discontinuous alignments show a lower capacity to modify the dominant thermal behaviour of their surroundings.

Furthermore, the analysis of ecosystem services shows that the Urban Green Infrastructure must be understood not only as a set of vegetation elements, but as a functional infrastructure capable of providing thermal regulation, generation of shade, reduction of incident radiation, improvement of climate comfort and other environmental benefits. The uneven distribution of these services between districts and hamlets shows the need to direct planning towards the reinforcement of those areas with a lower functional capacity, prioritising not only the increase of plant cover, but also the improvement of its quality, continuity and resilience in the face of climate change.

The main conclusion is that adaptation should not be limited to planting more specimens. It must be oriented towards increasing the effective canopy area, connecting existing masses, generating continuity in itineraries and gathering spaces, carrying out a selection of vegetation that genuinely contributes to the improvement of thermal comfort, reducing fragmentation and improving the quality of the current green areas.

This strategy must also incorporate the future resilience of the species. Vegetation can only act as climate infrastructure if it is able to persist under scenarios of higher temperature, drought and

water stress. Plant selection must combine shade capacity, climate tolerance, water efficiency, diversity and suitability for urban space.

Population vulnerability decisively modifies the distribution of climate risk

One of the main results of the study is that the areas with the worst environmental conditions do not necessarily coincide with those that present the highest final climate risk. The incorporation of social and demographic characteristics modifies the territorial interpretation obtained from temperature, vegetation and shade.

District 4 presents the most unfavourable environmental conditions of the urban centre. However, when population vulnerability is incorporated, District 1 becomes the main area of socio-environmental risk. This change shows that a moderate environmental level may acquire a high relevance when it coincides with a more sensitive population or with a lower adaptive capacity.

This result confirms that prioritisation should not be based solely on locating the hottest surfaces. It must also identify where heat may produce more serious social impacts. Environmental exposure and population vulnerability represent different dimensions and must be kept differentiated until their final integration.

The situation of the hamlets reinforces this conclusion. Although most present a moderate environmental risk, all reach a high socio-environmental risk level when population vulnerability is incorporated. Las Labores constitutes the most critical case, combining a high environmental risk with a high social vulnerability.

The common classification of the hamlets does not mean that they all present the same problems. The high level may respond to different combinations of temperature, shade deficit,

insufficient tree cover, demographic structure and socioeconomic conditions. Consequently, the measures must be adapted to the specific causes that generate the risk in each centre.

Participation complements and reinforces the territorial diagnosis, but it also reveals problems that the diagnosis alone cannot detect

The participatory information shows a relevant coincidence with the main patterns identified by means of the technical analyses. Citizen contributions reinforce the importance of the northern sector, the southern end and the central axis of the urban centre, especially around facilities, squares, pedestrian itineraries and spaces of everyday use.

The coincidence between perception and technical analysis is especially clear in the northern surroundings, related to District 4, and in the southern sector, corresponding to District 1. In these areas, the unfavourable environmental or socio-environmental conditions are also reflected in the everyday experience of the population.

However, participation provides additional value by identifying points of discomfort within districts globally classified with low or moderate risk. This does not represent a contradiction, but rather a difference of scale. The indices synthesise the average situation of a territorial unit, while citizens identify specific streets, squares or routes.

This difference shows that the census scale is adequate to prioritise general areas, but insufficient to define interventions on its own. Planning must combine the reading by districts with detailed analyses of public spaces, pedestrian routes and facilities.

The absence of contributions in the hamlets constitutes a specific limitation of the process. The

technical results make it possible to identify their vulnerability, but there is no equivalent validation based on local perception. Future participatory phases should correct this imbalance in order to incorporate the particular needs of these centres.

Adaptation must focus on the concurrence of factors

The study shows that no variable, considered independently, makes it possible to correctly identify all the priority areas. High temperatures, the lack of shade, the predominance of absorbent pavements, low tree cover, the fragmentation of vegetation and population vulnerability interact differently in each area.

Prioritisation must therefore be directed towards the spaces where several factors concur: unfavourable thermal conditions, deficit of shade and tree cover, high sealing, presence of vulnerable population and intense social use. This reading makes it possible to differentiate between areas that require a structural transformation and specific points where a localised intervention can generate significant improvements.

In the urban centre, District 1 must be considered a priority from the perspective of socio-environmental risk, while District 4 requires specific attention owing to its environmental conditions. The districts with medium risk should not be excluded, especially when they contain sensitive facilities, pedestrian routes or spaces flagged by citizens.

In the hamlets, the high final vulnerability demands a differentiated strategy. Las Labores presents a clear priority owing to the coincidence between high environmental and socio-environmental risk, but the rest of the centres equally require actions adapted to their specific deficits of shade, tree cover or urban structure.

The adaptation measures must combine the reinforcement of the Urban Green Infrastructure with actions on pavements, permeability, shade, accessibility and design of public space. Vegetation must act as part of an integrated urban strategy and not as an isolated or exclusively ornamental intervention.

In short, Huércal-Overa has a solid technical basis to move from diagnosis to planning. On the basis of these results, the following chapter establishes the criteria for defining strategic objectives, naturalisation guidelines and nature-based solutions adapted to the specific conditions of each district, hamlet and space of opportunity.

NEXT STEPS

The results obtained in this phase constitute the technical basis for advancing from the characterisation of climate risk towards the development of an Urban Naturalisation Strategy to Combat Heat in Huércal-Overa.

The diagnosis developed has made it possible to identify how thermal exposure, the deficit of shade and tree cover, the functionality of the Urban Green Infrastructure and population vulnerability are distributed. Likewise, it has made it possible to recognise relevant differences between the urban centre, its districts and the hamlets. The following phase must transform this information into a structured, territorialised and viable intervention proposal.

The development of the Strategy will not consist solely in transferring the results of the diagnosis to a planning document. It will be necessary to develop a specific process of analysis, selection and validation that makes it possible to determine which objectives should be pursued, where it is a priority to act and which types of intervention are the most appropriate for the environmental, urban and social conditions of each area.

Definition of the strategic framework

The following phase will begin with the definition of the strategic framework of urban naturalisation in the face of heat. To this end, the general and specific objectives that should guide the transformation of urban space and the improvement of its climate adaptation capacity will be established.

These objectives will be formulated on the basis of the results of this diagnosis, but they will have to be specified and prioritised considering their climate, environmental and social relevance, as well as their consistency with municipal policies, competences and capacities.

On the basis of the objectives, the naturalisation guidelines that will guide future interventions will be developed. These guidelines must define the criteria applicable to the increase of shade, the improvement of plant cover, the connectivity of the Urban Green Infrastructure, the adaptation of pavements, the permeability of the soil and the protection of the most vulnerable groups.

The definitive content of these guidelines will be one of the main results of the following phase and must be adapted to the specific characteristics of Huércal-Overa, avoiding the direct application of generic urban naturalisation models.

Identification and assessment of the spaces of opportunity

On the basis of the information generated, a detailed identification of the spaces with potential to incorporate naturalisation and heat-adaptation actions will be carried out.

The work will not be limited to locating the areas with high risk values, but will also analyse the physical availability of space, current uses, ownership, the presence of urban services, the intensity of use, the needs of the population and the technical viability of the possible interventions.

This process will make it possible to move from the general prioritisation by districts and hamlets to the delimitation of specific places of action. The identified spaces must be assessed and classified according to their problems, their improvement potential, the beneficiary population and the complexity of intervention.

The final selection will be carried out by means of a multi-criteria assessment that integrates the results of the climate and socio-environmental diagnosis with urban, technical and operational criteria. In this way, the Strategy will be able to establish a reasoned hierarchy of priority areas,

differentiating between immediate actions, pilot interventions and structural transformations of greater scope.

Design and assignment of solutions

Once the spaces of opportunity have been selected, the possible solutions applicable to each of them will be analysed. The following phase must study different naturalisation alternatives and assess their suitability for the specific conditions of each site.

The assignment of Nature-based Solutions will not be carried out automatically on the basis of the risk level. It will be necessary to consider the morphology of the space, its uses, the availability of land and water, the possible interferences with infrastructure, the maintenance needs and the real capacity of each solution to improve thermal comfort.

For each priority space, different options and combinations of intervention will be studied. These may include actions on trees, shrub and herbaceous vegetation, pavements, permeability, water management, the generation of shade and the functional reorganisation of public space.

The result will be a proposal of solutions adapted to each typology of space, accompanied by criteria that make it possible to justify their selection and facilitate their subsequent technical development.

Selection of plant species

The selection of species will be developed once the typologies of intervention and the specific conditions of the spaces in which action is proposed have been defined.

This phase will require analysing the compatibility of the species with the current and future

climate of Huércal-Overa, their water needs, their shade-generation capacity, their response to thermal stress, their adaptation to the available space and their management and maintenance requirements.

The results obtained in the analyses of resilience, cover, vigour and provision of ecosystem services will constitute the technical basis for this selection, but they must be complemented with specific criteria of establishment, urban functionality, diversity and compatibility with the conditions of each site.

The Strategy must establish differentiated recommendations by type of space and function, avoiding resorting to general lists of species unrelated to the specific needs of each action.

Assessment of viability and scheduling

The proposals developed must be subjected to an assessment of technical, economic and operational viability. This assessment will make it possible to determine which actions can be executed in the short term, which require greater technical development and which must be integrated into urban transformation processes in the medium or long term.

For each intervention, at least the land and water needs, the possible effects on infrastructure, accessibility, the establishment and maintenance costs and their compatibility with existing municipal planning and projects will be analysed.

On the basis of this assessment, a time schedule will be developed and criteria will be established for the progressive execution of the Strategy. Possible pilot actions that make it possible to verify the effectiveness of certain solutions before their application on a larger scale will also be identified.

Municipal validation and citizen participation

The development of the Strategy must be carried out in coordination with the various municipal areas involved in urban planning, the environment, green areas, mobility, public works, social services and maintenance.

This coordination will make it possible to incorporate information on planned projects, technical constraints, budgetary availability and municipal management capacity. It will also facilitate the integration of the proposals into other actions of transformation or improvement of public space.

The proposals must likewise be contrasted with citizens and local stakeholders. Participation will make it possible to validate the selection of spaces, incorporate information on their real uses, assess the acceptance of the solutions and detect needs or limitations that have not been identified by means of the technical analysis.

It will be especially important to extend this process to the hamlets, where this phase has not had sufficient participation to contrast the technical results with the perception of the resident population.

Development of the Strategy

The final result of the following phase will be the Urban Naturalisation Strategy to Combat Heat in Huércal-Overa.

The Strategy will integrate the framework of objectives, the naturalisation guidelines, the identification and prioritisation of the spaces of opportunity, the assignment of solutions, the selection of species, the assessment of viability and the time scheduling of the actions.

It must constitute an operational tool to guide municipal decisions, facilitate the subsequent development of projects, support the search for funding and coordinate the actions of naturalisation, climate adaptation and improvement of public space.

In this way, the following phase will make it possible to transform the climate diagnosis into an operational planning strategy, defining where to intervene, which problems to address, which solutions are most appropriate for each space and how to implement them in a progressive, viable manner consistent with the characteristics of the municipality.

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LUGIA PROJECT

HEAT WAVE RISK ANALYSIS AND ITS IMPACT
ON THE VULNERABLE GROUPS OF HUÉRCAL-OVERA

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